

Middle East University

Faculty of Education

STUDENT PERCEPTIONS OF SCHOOL CLIMATE AND SPIRITUALITY
IN EVANGELICAL SCHOOLS IN LEBANON

A Thesis

Presented in Partial Fulfillment
of the Requirements for the Degree
Master of Arts in Education

by

Hala Bitar

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THESIS ABSTRACT

Master of Arts in Education

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Title: Student Perceptions of School Climate and Spirituality in Evangelical Schools in Lebanon

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Historically, Evangelical schools were renowned for teaching the hearts and the minds of males and females from all religions and sects in Lebanon. The main questions of this study were to find out what the school climate and spirituality are, and if there is a correlation between them. Students from four Evangelical schools participated (577 students, males and females). School samples were varied in religious and socioeconomic backgrounds, geographical locations, and programs presented.

Results showed that students at Evangelical schools in Lebanon, from different religious backgrounds, genders, geographical locations were satisfied about their school climate. They were satisfied with their school's physical appearance, interactions, learning, discipline environment, culture and attitude, and school-community relations. Schools which are rich with various programs and activities reflected higher satisfaction of their students' perceptions of school climate.

Data also showed that students in this study were satisfied with the spirituality at their schools. Students perceived that their relationship with God, others, their own selves, and nature were generally satisfying. However, students' ideals for spirituality were higher than what they felt at school. Female students' ideals for spirituality were higher than male students' ideals. Grade 7 students had less positive perceptions of their spirituality at school than Grades 10, 11, and 12. Moreover, students in schools with Christian education programs reflected higher ideals of spirituality in relation to God than other schools, yet all students in the Evangelical schools under study perceived that they feel moderately spiritual at their schools.

School climate was found to correlate positively with students' spirituality (ideal and felt). The strongest correlation between school climate and spirituality was reflected in the school-community relations. Students in all schools perceived that their interactions with peers and teachers were the most influential factor in both the school's climate and spirituality. More positive spirituality at schools can be predicted when Evangelical schools effectively develop their school climate.

To God be the Glory

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CHAPTER 1

BACKGROUND

Early at the beginning of the nineteenth century, Protestant missionaries from churches in the USA and Scotland, as well as from the Anglican Church in Britain and Lutherans in Germany, brought the teaching of the Reformation to the Middle East. Lebanon, at that time occupied by the Ottoman Empire, was one of those very important places of concern for the missionaries. The aim of those missionaries was at first to evangelize Jews and Muslims. They believed that all people of the Middle East needed to experience the Evangelical spiritual reform and change as the missionaries have done. At the beginning, the aim was not to establish a church, but rather to change the hearts and minds of the people and revive the spirit. In case of spiritual revival, people used to join the nearest Christian community and church in their town. However, this did not last for long; the missionaries discovered that this strategy would not work for many reasons, and thus they considered establishing real Evangelical or Protestant communities as churches (Badr, 1992).

The titles “Evangelical” and “Protestant” are given to the same group, and both were used to name the new converts and communities. Many documents used these two names interchangeably to indicate the same group and church till our days. (Badr, Abou el Russ Slim, & Abou Nohra, 2005). The Lebanon Demographics Profile, 2016, indicates that for the Lebanese total population of around 4 - 4.4 million, the Christian population is divided into 21% Maronite, 8% Greek Orthodox, 5% Melkite Catholics, 4% Armenian Orthodox, 1% Protestants or Evangelicals, and 2% others. The Muslim population is divided into 27% Shia, 27% Sunni, 4.22%

Druze, and 0.88% Alawi. Likewise, the records of the Supreme Council of Evangelical Churches in Lebanon show that the number of the Evangelicals or the Protestant community in Beirut is one percent of the population, which is close to 40,000 people (Supreme Council Records, 2016).

What brought these missionaries to schools and education? The zeal of the Evangelical spirit to teach the Bible and the Word of God, and its aspiration to lead communities to read and hear the Word of God, led naturally to establishing primary and later secondary schools. Education and schooling were a pioneer tool and a mean of leading the revived community to spiritual growth and commitment. Girls' education was one of the most significant targets here, since women were considered inferior in education. The first girls' school in the Ottoman Empire was established in Istanbul in 1833 and the second in Beirut in 1835. This school continues in Beirut under the leadership of the National Evangelical Synod of Syria and Lebanon (Badr, Abo Russ Slim, & Abou Nohra 2005).

Evangelical schools in Lebanon have a long history with effective educational systems. During the mid-nineteenth century and the beginning of the twentieth century, many Protestants and Evangelical missionaries established schools and universities to spread the Word and the Love of God in Jesus. Womack (2012) and Fleishmann (2006) state that the American protestant missions under the ABCFM and the Presbyterian Board used the vernacular Arabic-English instruction, whereby they would teach in both languages (Arabic and English) in order to prepare people capable of influencing their local communities. The Protestant and Evangelical communities in Beirut are almost as old as these colleges and schools. The way the Protestants prepared their graduates was influential in many ways. Womack (2012) states that the national revival or *Alnahda* was led by students prepared by Protestant

schools and missions. Studying in Protestant mission schools provided a secular alternative to the limitations provided by the dominant traditional church hierarchy (Hourani, 1991; Hourani 1993). Students were able to find different vocational domains other than the priesthood or law. The word “secular” here means non-religious. By 1882, the student population of Protestant and Jesuit Christian schools was three times higher than that of any other Muslim or Turkish school. Early schools were established with very high academic standards and aims, in addition to being enriched by Biblical and Evangelical teachings. These missions targeted education first for girls with the aim of empowering them to write and read so they could read the Bible and teach it to the next generations (Badr, 1992; Jessup, 1910; Womack, 2012).

Fleischmann (2006) reports that the educational objectives of those mission schools were mingled with Evangelization agendas in addition to sociopolitical ideals. The mission schools and colleges enjoyed an excellent and prolonged reputation for equipping students and graduates with the required ingredients for good, holistic character, as evidenced by Womack’s assertion that “American Protestant teaching was understood as a tradition of freedom of thoughts and propagation of individual social welfare” (Womack, 2012, p. 13). The schools of the Protestant missions became fertile ground for such radical ideas as nationalism and justice. The teaching of those mission schools shook the dust off traditional culture and paved ways for human development.

Although these schools and educational centers were pioneers in participating in the development of modern Lebanon, they created a group of people who felt alienated in their own local lands, people who aspired to move to the West where they would feel integrated in the more developed western life (Womack, 2012). Regarding

the education of women, the role of the mission schools and colleges in enriching women's education focused on preparing a holistic curriculum where nurturing character and spirituality went side by side with nurturing the mind and academics. Girls were able to meet their needs in preparing good future wives and mothers and simultaneously well-equipped as educated women. While some might consider this approach to be alienating and ambiguous, this ambiguity of life model led many women to great achievements in different areas of life (Fleishmann, 2002; 2006).

Curricula for girls' schools are described as rich in music, sports, drama, Bible lessons, spiritual foundations, and home economics, in addition to excellent proficiency in languages, sciences, and history (Fleishmann, 2002; 2006). In general, the curricula at girls' schools produced students with proficiency in language and advanced academic achievement; however, these students remained alienated from their local cultures. The most influential Arab writers in the mid nineteenth century received their schooling in Christian schools. Some of these writers include Al Bustani and Faris Shidyak. Al Bustani was an Arab scholar who was converted to Protestantism and was hired by the Protestant mission to translate the Bible into Arabic (Fleishmann, 2002; 2006; Jessup, 1910).

It is noteworthy that American missionaries aimed at evangelism and what they reaped was very good education. They aimed at turning hearts to God and what they reaped resulted in high quality education. Fleischmann (2006) described this as follows: "Indeed, the academic offsprings at the seminary (first girls' school) from the start were rather impressive for the time. De Forest reports in 1853 that the students were reading a book on "moral philosophy," and during their history class, an atlas was "always open before them" (p. 278). The aim of education was to prepare graduates (specifically women, and later men), capable of benefiting from both

intellectual and spiritual teachings, and who could consequently carry the light and the blessings to their homes and their spheres of influence. In 1903-1904 the curriculum included arithmetic, geography, English, history and sciences (taken in English), physiology, natural philosophy, general history, chemistry, and astronomy. The schools' emphasis gradually changed from merely graduating good Christian wives to graduating modern educated women provided with all means of service needed for the future (Murre-van den Berg, 2005). The quality of schooling was described in the way that subsequently led their lives post-graduation. Some of the graduates went into medicine, nursing, and other professions. Later by 1914, the percentage of Muslim female students enrolled in Protestant schools increased to seventeen in one of the first schools in Beirut. The success story of the American female seminary or school in Beirut has been taken to other places in Lebanon such as Tripoli where a seminary was founded in 1872, and to Sidon where a school was founded in 1862 (Jessup, 1910).

However, despite their undeniable success, missionary schools experienced tension as of the mid nineteenth century between the mission leaders abroad and those leading in Lebanon. Tension rose regarding the choice of “conversion or civilization” of students (Womack, 2012, p. 7). Murre-van den Berg (2006) in her introduction to the book *New Faith in Ancient Lands*, mentions a case of a leading administrator of an American mission, Rufus Anderson, who strongly supported missions focusing mainly on conversion and refraining from extensive activities in higher education and medical care. The reaction of the local missionary leaders in Lebanon was very critical of Anderson and supportive of the secularization of the curriculum. Protestant piety continued to be instilled but only in educational settings where students can read Biblical verses daily but only during their chapel times and prayer. However, the

architects of this approach faced a main concern: they were aware that they needed to keep both Eastern Christians and Muslims interested in Protestant schools and to ensure that these groups did not withdraw from Protestant schools due to their conversion mission (Jessup, 1910; Khalaf, 2002).

British Protestant schools in Lebanon likewise followed a similar approach to education and faced similar challenges. In *Dare and Persevere* Scott (1960) summarizes the milestones of the work of the British mission in the East from 1860-1960, stating that missionary work in schools was classified as teaching accompanied by evangelism. Daily Bible lessons and prayers were strictly observed by the whole community. He adds that some families in the villages worried about the possibility of their children's conversion and they were very skeptical about it. He also adds that of the 525 schools in 'all Syria' at that time (all Syria refers to Syria and Lebanon), encompassing 3789 students, 105 national teachers, 24 women Bible teachers, and sixteen European workers, all were convinced that the primary goal of education was teaching the Word of God (p. 73). Memorization of the Bible verses was part of the daily curriculum beginning early in 1881. Students were required to complete memorizing the "100 Texts" put together by the Irish church missions. Students were encouraged to reflect on their faith and share confessions through prayer cycles, and several applied for church membership.

This did not go without oppositions from other Christian groups and denominations like the Maronite and the Orthodox Christians. Yet, this did not hinder the work of the mission to achieve its goals in evangelism. It was well-known that with the founding of Evangelical schools in Christian Maronite and Druze villages, concurrent Jesuit schools would emerge. Unlike their American counterparts, according to Scott, British Evangelical schools were not limited to schools for girls or

boys only, or elementary and secondary schools, but diversified to also include professional and technical schools for both able-bodied and handicapped students including the blind and paraplegic. Medical schools and schools of nursing were part of their interest as well. In addition to academic work, female students were taught needlework and weaving. Academic and spiritual formation went side by side, and students were encouraged to participate in different kinds of spiritual formation and fellowships (p. 73). Students from all religious backgrounds attested to the fact that their teachers were the best, since they encouraged students to be good Christians. Moreover, women graduates for the teaching profession in Muslim and Orthodox schools were praised for their excellent values that contributed to their outstanding and effective teaching.

The same mission and aims were adopted by the Baptist Evangelical schools which were established at the mid twentieth century. Baptist schools were enriched after establishing a Baptist community in Beirut by *Said Jeridini* in 1895, an Arabic speaking Christian from the Ottoman Empire who traveled to the USA, converted to the Baptist Evangelical faith, and returned to establish the first Baptist church in Beirut. This church started as a religious mission before undertaking schooling and work in education, unlike the American Protestant mission. For the Baptists both schooling and the printing press were ways of legitimizing the mission of Evangelism (Trexler, 2014). Late 19th century and early 20th century was the time when the Christian civilization appeared in the Middle East, according to Murre van den Berg (2006), and this is due to Christian institutions like schools which introduced Christian values and ethics. The first Baptist school was founded in 1949 when the Baptist mission resolved many political and geopolitical conflicts. This school too was built on the belief and need for evangelism. The school curriculum included both

oriental and American orientations, an issue which the Baptist church had long been struggling to resolve. The school continues till the present in the same location in Beirut, and despite most of its students being Muslim, it still continues its mission to teach the Bible along with preparing a generation equipped to face life with Christian beliefs and ethics (Trexler, 2014).

The Adventist mission, which was established in Beirut at the end of the nineteenth century, pursues similar aims. In his book about the Seventh-day Adventist Church in Lebanon, Nazirian (1999) describes how this mission started early as 1897 with a visit from Holser of the central European conference who visited Beirut and planned to publish books in Arabic. The European Seventh-day Adventist Mission headquartered in Darmstadt, Germany felt the sacred urge to enter the Middle East, including Lebanon, with the Adventist message. In 1901 L.R. Conradi toured the Middle East to identify possibilities of mission outreach and visited Daniel Bliss, president of the Syrian Protestant College (now AUB), and related printing press and was encouraged to establish the headquarters of the Middle East Adventist mission in Beirut. The mission later expanded with many dedicated missionaries and followers who were whole-heartedly in love with spreading the Word of God and the Seventh-day Adventist teachings. The first Adventist school in Lebanon was established in 1944 in the village of Aramoun in the district of Aley, followed by many schools and churches all over Lebanon. Only some of these schools are still functioning today.

The mission established schools which aimed to lead people—seen as an entity of heart, mind, and body—to a successful life. The schools, which are still active in Beirut, witness the work of this mission and its continued dedication to teaching the heart and mind together (Nazirian, 1999). The Adventist mission insists in its educational documents that teaching the Word of God and leading students to

spiritual formation are the most crucial aims in establishing schools (The Adventist School, n.d., para. 2).

From the above discussion, many conclusions can be drawn about the mission of Evangelical schools. In the first place, the schools' mission was primarily to evangelize or to prepare graduates extensively equipped with Christian values. Furthermore, schools provided programs specially designed to enable both genders, females and then males, to learn all kinds of knowledge. Additionally, schools had various programs and activities that addressed the holistic needs of the learner. Lastly, most of these schools were convinced that the aim of their education cannot be removed from the Christian Gospel and values with which they started. Most of these established schools by Evangelical missions are still in work and are renowned for their pioneering work in education and in graduating a generation characterized by elite and advanced skills.

In the electronic site, *Ethicsdaily.com*, Costa (2007) states that graduates of Evangelical schools are equipped with a well-rounded character which allows them to participate in many domains of the Lebanese society. He adds that graduates of Evangelical schools never get involved in terrorist or extremist activities, due to the high-quality, holistic, and open-minded education they receive (Costa, 2007).

These qualities have been observed by other scholars, (e.g., Sink, Cleveland & Stern, 2007) who state that “since the early 20thth century, Christian institutions have cultivated healthy student spirituality as a way in part, to enhance personal well-being and to cultivate psychosocial character development” (p. 1). Likewise in Lebanon, the results of Evangelical schooling and educational work are evident.

Since I started my work in 2001 as school chaplain and Christian educator at one of the Evangelical schools in Beirut, a question has been on my mind. During my

studies in education at Middle East University, covering many essential aspects of Christian Education in schools, one of the issues that interested me was the extent of the Christian identity of Evangelical schools and the ways in which Evangelical schools cultivate the spirituality of their students.

The Evangelical community in Beirut is small compared to other Christian communities like the Catholic-Maronite and the Orthodox. Despite that, the Evangelical community is considered important in the Christian fabric of the Lebanese community (Sabra, 2001). Although the Evangelical community is small, its educational institutions are viewed as some of the most flourishing and enduring in Lebanon. The Evangelical Fellowship of Schools in Lebanon notes the number of 35 Evangelical schools around Lebanon. Students in all Evangelical schools represent different segments of the Lebanese population in terms of location and demographic characteristics.

Problem Statement

Evangelical schools in Beirut were pioneers in leading a Christian mission. They were renowned for leading the hearts and the minds of their students towards the knowledge of God and human life. Evangelical schools traditionally cultivated a climate that helped in building students' Christian faith. Given the challenges presented by secularism, and the need to be accepted by various groups and systems, Evangelical schools have had to adapt their environment and programs. However, with the recent flood of secularism, and the ensuing struggle for survival among many Christian educational institutions, the question arises as to what has happened to the climate in Evangelical schools. Are the programs and the activities, the teachers' interactions with students, and other factors of school climate organized to support the growth of the students' minds as well as the growth of their spirituality? Are academic

programs and curricular endeavors set to motivate students' spirituality? Do Evangelical schools encourage interactions between students and teachers based on values and morals that lead to enriching students' spirituality? Do Evangelical schools lead in providing high-quality moral education that supports students' spirituality? Do the schools' emotional and physical settings enhance students' spirituality?

Purpose Statement

This study aims to examine students' perceptions of school climate and spirituality in Evangelical schools in Lebanon. It examines what the school climate and spirituality are like at Evangelical schools; it also aims to examine the relationship between students' perceptions of Evangelical schools' climate and students' spirituality, and to observe whether the climate in Evangelical schools correlates with students' spirituality.

Research Questions

The main question of this research paper is: Do the student perceptions of school climate in Evangelical schools correlate with students' spirituality? (ASSC and SHALOM 2). This question leads to many sub questions: (1) What is school climate? (ASSC and interviews). (2) What are the student perceptions of school climate? (ASSC tool and interviews with students and spiritual life director) (3) What is spirituality? (SHALOM 2) (4) What are students' perceptions of spirituality? (SHALOM 2) and (5) What is the relation between students' perceptions of school climate and spirituality? (Correlation and interviews) (Index A, Instruments).

Hypothesis

The null hypothesis is that school climate and learning environment have no correlation with students' spirituality and do not reflect students' spirituality. In

Evangelical schools, the programs and activities, academics, curricula, student-teacher interactions, and schools' psychological and physical settings do not correlate with students' spirituality.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

Many factors explain why and how Lebanese education has been influenced by western education. The first is the Evangelical, Protestant and Christian missions and the resulting pervasiveness of American, British, and French curricula and languages (Womack, 2012). A second factor is the French occupation and its role in spreading Christian mission schools and French language-based programs. The third is indirectly related to the Lebanese Civil War.

Secularism

The secular movement and the influx of secular thoughts were natural reactions to the westernization of schools' programs and curricula. However, secularism did not eliminate the religious character of Lebanese society. Secularism created a new category in religious teaching. Dichotomy between secularism and religion was made without eliminating either of them. Kuusisto, Poulter, and Kallioniemi (2016) emphasize this point, highlighting how religious tradition in the public sphere is sometimes actually just cultural, as maintained in secular societal settings such as schools, and how secular worldviews are often falsely perceived as more "neutral" than religious worldviews. Although every individual holds his or her unique worldview which is not "neutral" but is, always value-laden, some try to hide their religiosity and privatize it for the fear of being categorized as religious. Kuusisto, Poulter, and Kallioniemi's research shows that in school communities within a secular societal setting, being religious was often perceived in pupils' peer

groups as being not modern or publicly accepted. The separation between the secular and the religious stems from defining religion as biased or cultural, whereas secularism is viewed as neutral and intellectual. The secular world is unaware of the possibility that people who are religious or spiritual can relate to the secular world while maintaining their religiosity.

However, this does not mean that societies are dichotomized into religious and secular sections, rather, it is a presentation of what might be secular and religious without eliminating either. Secular society might be biased in understanding the flexibility of some religious groups in interacting with societies and forming multidimensional worldviews. At the same time, this does not eliminate the tendency of some religious communities to live their own closeted world without any relation or influence by the secular world. Sabra (2005), in a public lecture presented at the American University of Beirut, describes the tendency of one of the university presidents, influenced by the thoughts of liberal theologian, Lyman Abbot, to reduce the religious elements of the curriculum and other aspects of university life. In 1885, a transformation began at the university and teaching the Bible was no longer regarded as pursued for the sake of Evangelism, but rather for building a good character and nurturing appropriate values in students. Referring to statements made by AUB's president Dadge in 1923, when this president states that:

To develop the spiritual nature of our students, we do not propose to proselytize or to emphasize names and forms. To us Protestantism means religious freedom, and as a Protestant institution we wish to give our students freedom of worship and freedom of belief. We believe religion is not an ulterior aim of education; it is not a quantity of tangible facts to be taught, or a creed to be subscribed to: Religion is not for the chapel alone, but can be

found in the spirit of honest student, good sportsmanship, and consecration to the welfare of mankind. It must be learned in every phase of the university life. (Sabra, 2005, p. 10-11)

Sabra (2005) continues to describe the phase, from 1975 onwards, of the Protestant university, and he calls it the phase when secularism started to grow. He writes: “The AUB was changing from an institution which prided itself on developing men’s souls as well as their minds, to one whose concern was above all academics. There was less emphasis on the development of the whole personality” (p. 13). What Sabra (2005) noticed here is that Lebanese society has always been religious and will continue to be so, while its universities are seemingly neutral. By removing universities from their religious identities and activities, is it possible to develop graduates who are more authentic and more capable of engaging in the future life of the country? Poulter, Riitaoja and Kuusisto (2014) explain that all worldviews are value-laden and often also combine elements of religious and non-religious traditions—after all, people can relate to both their religious societies and secular thoughts and ideas. Helve (2016) describes the ability of today’s young generations to relate to multidimensional worldviews beside their own contextual religious formation. Young generations’ ideologies are influenced by but not limited to those of their parents and extended families, rather each individual reflects a new worldview. Thus, in the case of young generations, the abyssal line between secular societies and religious elements and traditions within them is hard to delineate.

What is necessary is a rethinking of the relation between secularism and religion. Cox (2013), in his book, *The Secular City*, which was initially published in 1965, outlines the secular relatedness to religion even before Christ and describes how religion, particularly Christianity, has encouraged a secular response to change. He

welcomes the efforts of the secular society rather than opposing them and challenges the readers to respond particularly to the social teachings of Jesus Christ. He explains that and faith and belief would follow. Cox's definition of secularism is based on that of Dutch theologian C. V. Van Peursen who said:

Secularization is the deliverance of man, first from religious and then from metaphysical control over his reason and his language. It is the loosing of the world from religious and quasi-religious understandings of itself, and the dispelling of all closed worldviews, the breaking of all supernatural myths and sacred symbols. It represents the "de-fatalisation of history," the discovery by man that he has been left with the world on his hands, that he can no longer blame fortune or furies for what he does with it. Secularization occurs when man turns his attention away from worlds beyond and towards this time. (Cox, 2013, p. 1)

Cox (2013) is calling on modern man to flee from mystical faith and limited beliefs to shape his life based on modern thinking and reasoning. Cox is not against faith; rather he is against the fatalism of thinking in God.

Cox (1965) argues that: "Jesus did not try to assume worldly power, secular power at all, but confronted the corrupt powers, both religious and secular of His time, from a position, a freed position, of non-violence and [lack of involvement] in the running of the society" (p. 9). He was concerned that people live in a changing world with a static religion and theology. He was also concerned with negativity and the insignificance of some religious teachings to human life and their suitability in a modern world. His answer is that secularism is the solution to this indifference and static state.

Likewise, Hotam (2016) presents a suggestion to rethink the relation between secular concepts and religious ones in the context of education. In the article “*Rethinking the Relation between Secular ‘Consciousness’ and Religion*” points to Habermas who describes the dichotomy theory between religion and reason. Hotam (2016) argues that secularism and religion are in dialectic phase with secularism having its roots in religious concepts. Dichotomy is no longer used to indicate more separation, but rather it must reflect the channels of communication while expressing the separated identities. In the post-secular world, neither religion nor secularism can stand without transformation. Hotam (2016) discusses the dialectic relation in the concept of liberation. In the heart of secularism is the concept of liberation, liberation from religion. But is liberation from religion secularism’s only concern? And is liberation an external thought separated from religion? Hotam’s (2016) response is that “Transformation is the key word here that refers to change in the location of the concept where it does not destroy its earlier attributes, but preserve them.” (p. 291).

Acceptance of secular movements was not only a reaction and result of westernization of curricula and thoughts, but also a result of the civil war that has affected Lebanese life and culture for thirty years. Civil war and its resultant separation of Lebanese society into religious sects and denominations created a natural tendency to find solutions based on secularization. Secularization here is an aspiration to delete the rigid religious and sectarian effects on the Lebanese society, and a call to unite the Lebanese nationality under one humanitarian cause. Sabra (2001), as a religious Evangelical thinker and professor of Systematic theology, called for secularization as a solution to limit the dominance of limited fanatic religions and thinking. Sabra is calling here to preserve the essence of religion yet, he considers the valor of secularism in playing reason over fanaticism. As Poulter et al (2014, p. 2)

state: “The school as public institution is a place where subjectivities and identities are constructed and the spheres of the private and the public are negotiated.”

Therefore, we cannot help schools from being spiritual by claiming secular or/either religious identity. Both identities are in need to be clarified, examined and presented in a necessarily manner. Education that is based on one part of the human identity will not lead to a holistic approach, but rather to fragments which cannot describe the original. Are we, by highlighting one part and ignoring the other, able to present the whole truth? Can we, by presenting in our schools western secularism, reflect the true identity of our culture, and society? Poulter, Riitaoja and Kuusisto (2014) present that contemporary societies are so diverse and complex where the division between religious and secular is not easily done: they write about ‘Secular Christian’ societal hegemony in which the maintained ‘religious’ traditions are indeed secularized. They also refer to empirical findings showing that students and children are very much aware of the complexity and fluidity of their own and parents’ religious identity. Therefore, societies and educational settings have tendencies in modern times to develop programs where students can have vivid identities which are not based on one notion rather on many, contextual and inter subjective ones. Secularism therefore has to be rethought and understood in the framework of an intellectual call to be neutral and objective and not ejective to religion without reason.

The private Christian schools had to face the threat of both the civil war and secularism, and had to preserve their identities. As a reaction, some Evangelical schools highlighted their secular identity and kept their religious identity in second place. Others are still in the phase of searching for solutions, and many others in response to solving sectarian issues, hid their religious identity totally under the humanitarian and ethical umbrellas.

School Climate

In order to get a closer understanding of the Evangelical schools' climate and its role in student spirituality, we are going to define in general terms school climate and spirituality and highlight the relationship between them.

School leaders and administrators do not unite in their definition of school climate. Some do consider that school climate is the physical surrounding of the school. Others, define school climate as limited to programs and resources. Some school leaders do plan and prepare for it, and some do not consider it as part of their learning and teaching systems. Although all researchers do not stand for one definition of what school climate is, they do agree that school climate has profound influence on students' learning and life in school. Loukas (2007) defines school climate as: "The feelings and attitudes that are elicited by a school's environment, are referred to as school climate" (p. 1). Lukas (2007) presents that researchers also agree that it "is a multidimensional construct that includes physical, social, and academic dimension" (p. 1). Thapa, Cohen, D' Alessandro, and Guffey (2012) state that: "The school climate is based on patterns of people's experiences of school life and reflects norms, goals, values, interpersonal relationships teaching and learning practices, and organizational structures" (p. 2). Marshall (2004) further defines the school climate as the multidimensional construct of factors that influence not only students, but teachers, parents, and the whole community. In this way we cannot limit the school climate to one aspect or factor, it includes all these aspects of a school community.

The school climate includes the physical aspect where all school's physical appearances do influence students and inspire their learning and growth beside their emotions and wellness. The social dimension aspect has a great part in this definition where interactions with all the school community influence learning too. The

academic aspect which is not only limited to classroom instructions, but to every feature that enhances students' academic achievement and learning. Reflecting on all of the previous factors and dimensions, the school climate can be defined as the direct and indirect tools and aspects that are visible or not, and are planned for or not, and that can be considered part of the school climate. According to this understanding, we can also conclude that the school climate can be of high impact on all school learning processes. It can be an indirectly normative, positive or negative partner in the learning and teaching process.

Although it is hard to have a definitive succinct definition, since each school reflects and corresponds to a specific culture and school of thought. A summary of all what was stated above shows that the school climate is all what we see, feel, perceive, and interact with in a specific school location and in a specific time and place.

School Climate and its Influence

School climate, understanding it, planning for it, and assessing it can be of immense help in leading change. Researchers, using empirical data, have found that school climate affects students' self-esteem (Hanson, 2004). It affects also a wide range of students' mental, emotional, and health outcomes (Durham, Bettencourt & Connolly, 2014; Kidger, Donovan & Gunnell, 2012; Fan, Corkin & Williams, 2011). They also found a positive correlation between school climate and the use of drugs and substance abuse, and positive correlation and prediction of better psychological well-being, and school absenteeism (Loukas, 2007; Rubin, 2004). Researchers also found a more powerful influence on students' motivation, academic success, school aggression and harassment, and life development (Marshall, 2004; Cohen, Pickeral & McCloskey, 2009).

Another factor of influence to the school climate, is the relational factor. Positive school climate leads to positive relations and better behavioral attitudes. Interactions with peers and teachers can lead either to positive behavioral attitudes or to negative ones (Sinclair, 1970; Skinner & Belmont, 1993). Researchers also showed that character education programs and activities lead to high academic achievement and less behavioral problems (Aldrige, Ala'i & Fraser, 2014; Loukas, 2007; LeBlanc, Swisher, Vitaro & Tremblay, 2008; Fraser, 2012). School climate does influence spiritual life of students. The research which was done by Sink, Cleveland and Stern (2007) found a correlation between positive spirituality and healthy functioning across a variety of developmental domains in a students' life. Previous research literature indicates that school climate affects all dimensions of students' life, and it either elevates school life and learning quality or lowers them.

Dimensions of School Climate

Then what should be developed in school climate? Which of its parts can make a difference in the life of the students? According to the previous definitions of school climate, a construct of multidimensional parts and factors is found. These factors and parts are: The physical, the social, the ethical, the organizational, and the cognitive ones (Loukas, 2007). These factors and parts can be explained and used as measures and standards of school climate in every school.

The physical dimension measures the school safety and the students' physical wellness. It concentrates on how school rules can reflect the school's identity, and how they are consistent and can form a positive enforcement of students' wellness from verbal and physical abuse. Safety is not limited to rules and norms, but to senses and feelings of belonging to schools. The feeling of social and emotional security form a part of this dimension too (Cohen, Pickeral & McCloskey, 2009). When the

school rules witness to fairness, love, care, safety, and goodness of all the students, rules indirectly will lead to enriching valuable direct character (Loukas, 2007).

Another important dimension with which to assess and measure school climate is the teaching and learning one. Does the school climate support students in their learning? Do all teaching practices form positive responses and encourage positive risk taking, academic challenge, and opportunities to demonstrate knowledge and skills in a variety of ways? School climate can support the students in forming many learning skills like, according to Cohen et al. (2009, para. 1): “conflict resolutions, reflections and responsibilities, ethical decisions, and inclusive effective listening.”

One more dimension in measuring the school climate is the interpersonal interactions. School climate can elevate quality interactions between peers, students and teachers. It can help in building positive discussions, caring community, and supportive bonds. Previous research indicates that in schools, there is positive correlation between fairness and personal care of adults and less bullying and negative interactions with peers (Loukas, 2007; Tubbs & Garner, 2008). When teachers support the students, and interact positively with them, the students are more likely to be engaged and behave appropriately (Skinner & Belmont, 1993). Moreover, teachers’ positive care of their students will encourage positive models of interaction between peers, and between students and their parents (Robin, 2004).

The final dimension of school climate tackled here includes the school programs and resources that support a positive environment. The institutional environment that includes school connectedness and physical surroundings are of high value to school climate. They enhance how students feel and how these feelings of belonging can enhance their learning. Cleanliness, order and appeal of facilities,

adequate resources, and available material can lead to positive responses in all school processes (Cohen et.al, 2009; Fan, Williams, & Corkin, 2011). The challenging question here is how can schools design these dimensions in a way that can lead to reflect the school identity and students' spirituality?

Students' Perceptions

The question of this research is if the school climate at Evangelical schools correlates with students' spirituality. How do students perceive their school climate and how does it influence their spirituality? Why is the perception question addressed here? We address perceptions because we understand that each student reacts to social, mental, emotional instructions in unique ways within the group. Fan, Williams and Corkin (2011) state this in the following: "Students' perceptions of school climate are not only associated with features of school climate within which students are situated, but also are shaped by their individual characteristics and experiences." (p. 2). According to Rogers (1951), individuals react to experiences psychologically according to internal resources and individual personal understandings. Therefore, we might find varieties of responses in perceptions of school climate. This might not relate to what it meant to be in the school. Understanding this factor will lead us to understand that school climate dimensions and factors together can affect comprehensively and consistently students' life. We are not to seek personal perceptions of individuals, rather we are seeking the impact of the school climate on a variety of students and how they perceive this impact when they are in school.

School Climate and School Culture

Most researchers agree that school climate and school culture overlap in their definition as concepts. According to MacNeil, Parter & Busch (2009), school climate and culture were defined by different people in the following manner. Hoy et al. (1991) made a distinction between them in the way that where school climate was viewed from psychological perspective, culture was viewed from anthropological perspective. Climate leads to behavior factors where culture leads us to understand more about norms and values of the school as an organization. Ornstein (2004) described that school culture as part of school climate and considered that school climate is a very important factor to work on. Schein (1985; 1996) considered that school culture is norms, rituals, values, and climate. Hoy and Feldman (1999) considered that culture is shared standards and climate is shared insights, yet the difference between them is so small. In all, climate was considered to have fewer concepts than culture which is more descriptive and symbolic and concluded that climate presents fewer problems in terms of empirical measurements. Most of the difference sets on that climate deals with the perceptive part of school environment, and culture deals with conceptive part of it. School climate seeks to measure students' perception of their school environment where culture in general deals with concepts of values and norms of the organization.

Teaching practices, diversity, and the relationships among administrators, teachers, parents, and students contribute to school climate. Although the two terms are somewhat interchangeable, school climate refers mostly to the school's effects on students, whereas school culture refers more to the way teachers and other staff members work together. (ASCD, n.d., para.1)

In this study, school climate refers to perceptions of experiences students have encountered in a specific place and community. These experiences are related to many domains like the physical, the interpersonal interactions, the academic, and the programs and resources of the school in a specific community. In this study, the school culture is explicit in the school climate as values, morals, traditions related to this community. Yet, there will be no study of the schools' cultures separately from the school climate. In this study, the school climate will be studied and described using a survey developed by the Association for the Study of School Climate (ASSC, 2016).

This study focuses on the dimensions of school climate and their importance in assessing school climate, while acknowledging the role of school culture, especially since the research will address the culture of Evangelical schools and its role in cultivating the spiritual life of their students.

Spirituality

The definitions of spirituality are wide and vary from secular to religious worlds. Definitions differentiate between spirituality as an experience or as a discipline. In this study, I focus on spirituality as an experience with its varying definitions that incorporate many contexts and fields, including the secular. In *Defining and Assessing Spiritual Health* (2012), Francis, Penny, and Barker argue that when defining spirituality, we must consider both the religious and the non-religious realms, as this then includes all dimensions of spirituality.

The *New Dictionary of Theology* (1987) defines spirituality as “ones’ entire life as understood, felt, imagined, and decided upon in relationship to God, in Christ Jesus, expressed by the Holy Spirit” (p. 972). Every person is spiritual and needs to nurture his/her spirituality (Komonchak, Collins & Lane, 1987). Paul the apostle in

the Scripture understands his life as a very spiritual life in Christ, a relationship which pours out of the spirit of Christ and recreates men and women in Christ. This experience with Christ leads to bearing others' burdens and pains (The Epistle of Philippians). *The New Dictionary of Theology* also presents the modern world definition of spirituality with Sandra M. Schneider who explains spirituality as "self-transcendence which gives integrity and meaning to life by situating the person with the horizon of ultimacy" (p. 981).

The philosophical basis of this definition suggests that there is no separation between the material and the spiritual; both include a capacity for self-transcendence through knowledge and love. Philosophically, all humans are spiritual and able to actualize this basis through establishing relationships. Self-transcendence is religiously based on a relationship with God and reflected in relations with others. It is the relationship with God poured in the life of faith, hope, and love which is the basis for each spiritual self. The starting point for this relation is the experience, and the issue of "the self" is the central issue of the definition of spirituality in modern Christian thinking. As Schneider (1987, p. 983) in the *New Dictionary of Theology* writes: "Development is a matter of recognizing and receiving one's true self." The Christian definition of spirituality is based on the work of the Holy Spirit in both self-actualization and in the relationship with others and with God. Christian spirituality therefore is trinitarian: the self, the other, and God; it is also Christological, since Christ is at the center; and ecclesial religious experience, since it reaches to the whole body of Christ in the loved church. The proper need for developing spirituality is contemplation and intellectual affective capacities working together. As defined in *New Dictionary of Theology* (1987), spirituality is a matter of unity and oneness with God. Therefore, spirituality is a pattern of discovering the true self, the true God, the

true choices, and ever greater freedom and awareness of life in connectedness with self and God.

Another study of spirituality is presented by Philip Sheldrake (n.d), in his work, *The Study of Spirituality* who defines spirituality as: “the desire of individuals and groups to enter into a conscious relationship with God, to worship, to formulate their deepest values, and to create an appropriate lifestyle in dialogue with their beliefs about God, people, and creation” (p. 162). Sheldrake (n.d.) believes that spirituality and theology are mutually interactive partners that respect each other’s autonomy. Both spirituality and moral theology find a common language in renewal understanding of personhood and grace. There is now a basic unity between spiritual and moral life. In other words, both moral theology and spirituality are concerned with exploring new understandings of virtues and character. Moral theologians become more aware that the ultimate guide to goodness lies not in rules but in the activity of the Holy Spirit within humans.

Beyond the Christian definitions, Fraser and Grootenboer (2014) present in their article *Nurturing Spirituality in Secular Classrooms*, definitions of spirituality that are basically related to the secular world. In their article about spirituality in the New Zealand context, they stated that “spirituality is trying to be everything to everyone, and therefore nothing to anyone at all” (p. 308). Spirituality is regarded as source for meaning and inspiration for life and could be not. British Humanist Association (1993), as addressed by Fraser and Grootenboer (2014) states that spirituality comes from people’s deepest humanity and appreciation of and wonder at the natural world, intellectual achievement, and physical activity. In this manner, spirituality is the reflective need people aspire to address a need to express wonders and amazement at the work of humanity. Wright (2000) and Thatcher (1999) present

practical definitions of spirituality as “our concern for the ultimate meaning and purpose of life” (p. 7). Spirituality is living a meaningful life in response to the deepest truths of the universe. Definitions might vary here to respond to all fields of knowledge, values, ethics, cultures and commitments. With these varied definitions, a teacher might wonder how to lead teaching instruction!

Claxton (2002) confirmed that there is no confirmed definition or agreed definition of spirituality, as people may differ in their interpretations. Instead of defining spirituality, he affirms that we need to look for what is common experience in specific community. We need to look for what kinds of qualities that might be included and give life a meaning (sense of life) and sense of belonging and relatedness to specific part of the world. Claxton also insists indirectly on relatedness in his attempt to define spirituality. Connectedness to the world convictions and mysteries is what brings peace to mind and spirit. Claxton refuses to relate spirituality to the world of theology and religions and instead insists on its relatedness to the psychological needs of any human being. Piechowski (2003) describes spirituality as based on childhood experience of being timeless, one with nature and God in everything. A feeling of sense of self of achieving high states of awareness.

The main definition recognized and focused on through this study is the definition presented by Francis, Penny, and Barker (2012) which highlights the definition and the work of Fisher (1998) who links spirituality to four domains of connectedness and in relation to the personal, the communal, the environmental, and the transcendental, which is the connectedness to God and mystic events. Fisher (1998) defines spirituality after studying many manifestations of many definitions. He states that spirituality relates to a person’s awareness of the existence and experience of inner feelings and beliefs that give purpose, meaning, and value to life. Spirituality

helps individuals to live in peace with themselves, to love God and their neighbors, and to live in harmony with the environment. For some, “spirituality involves encounter with God, a transcendent reality, which can occur in or out of the context of an organized religion, whereas for others, it needs to involve no experience or belief in the supernatural.” (p. 16). To understand this definition in detail, we need to understand how Fisher got his inclusions through the study of Ingersoll (1994), Tillich (1967), and Ellison (1983).

Ingersoll (1994) states that individuals may perceive God in many areas as theistic which means related and transcendent, atheistic which means a refused God, pantheistic which means related to absolute force, and “panentheistic” which means found in all things, flowing through all things, and transcending all things. Aside from noticing the various aspects of perceiving God, there are different perceptions of spirituality related to the different perceptions of the divinity as categorized by Ingersoll. First perception appear beside these categories is “spiritual rationalism” as stated by Fisher (1998, p. 17). This means when humans refuse the presence of the spirit in all human beings, the question of spirituality does not disappear but is rather moved to the rational category. As Fisher makes clear: “Every spirit can be shaped by human experience, hopes, and uses of times” (p. 17). The second perception leads to understanding spirituality as unionism, which means oneness of all spirits with God and nature. The third perception focuses on spirituality as dualism, which means separating the spiritual and the material, the sacred and secular, the subjective and objective, and the tension that appears in between. The fourth perception leads to understanding spirituality as multidimensional unity which, according to Tillich (1968) is when “the spirit is not above, nor the same as the mind”, but both working side to side (p. 28). Tillich states that “reason is the structure of both mind and world,

whereas spirit is their dynamic actualization in personality and community” (p. 63).

The business of reason is to structure knowledge and the business of spirit is to give it life and activates it to the person and to its surrounding life. Tillich suggests that we look at the human as multidimensional unity who co-exist in harmony and in relation with nature and others. Therefore, there is a recognition the relational part in defining spirituality and spiritual health. Young (1984) states that interrelatedness of mind and body and spirit in peace relations with the love of others, relations with nature and God are the focus of any beliefs and convictions.

Tillich (1967) recognizes that morality, culture, and religion clarify one another; they constitute the unity of the spirit. Morality is essentially related to culture and religion. Culture provides the content for morality, the concrete ideas of personality and community, and the changing laws of ethical wisdom. “Religion gives to morality the unconditional character of the moral imperative, the ultimate moral aim, the reunion of the separated in a gape, and the motivating power of grace” (p. 95). If we separate morality and culture from religion in existence, we get what is considered secular. Ellison (1983) believes that:

It is the spirit of human being that enables and motivates us to search for meaning and purpose on life, to seek supernatural or some meaning which transcends us. It is the spirit that provides some sense of energizing directions and orders. The spiritual dimension does not exist in isolation from our psyche and soma, but provides an integrative force. (p. 33)

Therefore, there is a need to involve the whole person, the whole experience of culture, morality, religion, and any related existential facts to the life of humans and their quests. This holistic view can lead to a balance in life which Fisher terms as “spiritual health” (p. 35).

Secular, theological, psychological and mixed definitions recognize and highlight directly and indirectly the most important aspects of spirituality that Fisher highlights in his definition. However, to place these definitions into the context of Evangelical schools and communities, the specific experience and characteristics of the Evangelical schools and their related communities must be understood.

We need to understand that the characteristics and experiences of the Evangelical community or communities and churches in Lebanon are distinctive. According to Sabra (2001), Evangelical communities have two main characteristics: first, the “*pietistic*” community, and second the “*cultural*” community. This distinction will help explain the wide differences between two groups of Evangelicals in their practice of spirituality at their churches and educational institutions, and this will lead to a definition of spirituality in an authentic Evangelical sense. Another point is the difference between “*religiosity*” and “*spirituality*”. Mixing both titles and definitions might lead to one limited definition of both, either secular or religious. What are the “*pietistic*” characteristics of the community? And what are the “*cultural*” characteristics of the community?

Sabra (2001) presents the challenges the Evangelical community faces in its desire to be an ecumenical community. He presents two characteristics in order to direct both “*pietistic*” and “*cultural*” Evangelical communities to future needs. The “*pietistic*” community and Evangelicals are a group who believe in the spiritual birth and the spiritual personal revival. They concentrate on the personal confessional attitude towards God and community. These characteristics concentrate on beliefs, faith, and renewal according to the Word of the Bible. Salvation is a central message, more so than what theological studies can find and lead to. Evangelism is central to this community since salvation is at stake for every believer. Good preaching and

Christian teaching are what lead the person to believe and convert and what is called “salvific teaching.” Other faiths are in need of changing and conversion to be part of the people of God. The Holy Bible is also at the center and the friend of every believer. The Word of God is infallible and does not need explanation. All good works are results of faith in God as proclaimed in the Bible, and all that any Christian does is a way to evangelize the Word of God. In contrast, the cultural Evangelical characteristics focus on liberal cultural thoughts that emerged from the teaching and culture of early missionaries. “*Cultural* Evangelicals examine the liberal thoughts in life, religion, and faith. All that matters are to liberate the mind and the spirit from blind tradition. Christianity is a mental religion in addition to providing spiritual experiences and liberating thoughts that refuse to recognize the work of superstition and declare the work of the message of God as a message of change. Cultural Evangelicals are those who believe that God works in all; therefore, they easily mix with other religions such as Islam and other denominations. The cultural Evangelicals are free from the dominance of the religious leaders and their traditions. They believe in God, the Love of Jesus, and the Word of God, but they do not emphasize the literal inspiration of the Bible. They do relate to some explanations and symbolic references and to some actions written in the Bible. Their Evangelical heritage is their pride, especially when mind was supreme to tradition and to limited Christian habits and old cultures. In attempts to present these two characteristics, Sabra calls on both groups and communities and characteristics to unite to define and reflect a true positive characteristic where both *pietistic* and *cultural* Evangelicals can together look for positive and constructive character and can seek a comprehensive Evangelical identity.

While closely considering Evangelical communities and their related schools in Lebanon, one cannot only understand the variety of characteristics of Evangelicals even within one group or community. This in turn affects how things are translated to a definition of spirituality, and how these communities and groups plan and orient their students and institutions into spirituality. In Pietistic groups, spirituality is religiosity, whereas in cultural groups, religiosity is part of spirituality, and at the same time may not lead to it at all. The question then arises: what is religiosity and what is spirituality?

Spirituality is as presented in the passages above, and in all definitions, secular and religious, cannot be limited to specific culture, religion, practices, convictions, and any group. According to the definitions above, every human is spiritual even though he or she is not religious. Lawton (2003) states that spirituality is giving people the chance to express themselves, while religiosity is belonging to a specific thinking. Spirituality can be religious where a person can find place in God and his love, while religiosity is limited to specific actions, laws, and practices more than what the state of mind can reason. In this manner, spirituality can be more expressive, flexible, and individual. "Religion is manmade; spirituality is innate" (Fahlberg & Fahlberg, as cited in Fisher, 2009, p. 9). Religion is related to institutions, while spirituality is a personal experience with transcendent power, and it might go beyond any religious fellowship. Religion can be one of the ways of helping and embracing spirituality, but it cannot define it. Spirituality might be subjective and emotive, and might touch the hearts because it deals with the very essence of being and existence. Do we need God in spirituality? What if God is not in one of the dimensions? Can we replace this supreme transcendent power? Can we replace this experience with the transcendent? What shall we put in its place? In his research about the importance of

relating with God for school students' spiritual well-being, Fisher reports that most of the students highlight the need to relate to God in their spiritual growth. Students from different Christian backgrounds reflect that God is a main source for inspiration and spiritual well-being. This inspiration of God can come from many close interactions like parents, peers, religion teachers, and community. Yet, many refer to God himself as a source of inspiration and guidance for spiritual well-being. The school ethos here is also highlighted and reflected in many ways and through many persons, mainly teachers.

Based on the above presented review of previous literature on spirituality and the specific characteristics of the Evangelical community in Lebanon, this study utilizes a definition. This definition recognizes the definition of Fisher (1998) and its four domains as a main guide for this study. The definition of Fisher (1998) comprehensively combined the religious and the secular definitions through presenting spirituality in its four domains. Therefore, spirituality here is defined as: an "awareness of existence" and an experience of "inner feelings and beliefs" related to a search for meaning in life in connectedness and relation to the transcendent God/divine, self, others, and nature. This experience and awareness lead people to experience peace with God/Divine, themselves, others, and nature. People build a relationship with Him/divine. This relation is reflected in drawing horizons for relationships with oneself, one's community, and with creation. This definition recognizes the Christian and the religious spirituality which is based on a relation with God/divine or transcendent, knowing him, experiencing him, interacting with him, and reflecting him. This could be practiced and shown in many ways such as seeking knowledge of God/divine, prayers, meditating, singing praises, and so on. Relating to oneself and accepting "the self" based on the deep understanding of the love of

God/divine is shown in many ways: practicing compassion and life of ethics with the whole community, and seeking understanding of different meanings of life with others. This relationship with God/Divine creates awareness of high values of justice, equity, and environmental sensitivity. The Christian faith does not deny the importance of “the self” as central to every experience and relatedness in life. This definition also recognizes the holistic approach to spirituality where relating only to God/Divine or to anyone of the four domains separately from the others cannot reflect comprehensive definition to spirituality. SHALOM 2 tool, which is used in this study will be guiding tool in presenting this definition too (Fisher, 1998).

The essential question here is how the climate at Evangelical schools can help in shaping adolescents’ spirituality? Is there any specification or study that indicates any difference from other schools? Can school climate shape students’ spirituality? What kind of programs and activities can be presented here? Are teachers and educational facilitators called on to be involved in this process? What is their role?

The Role of School Climate in Shaping Adolescents’ Identity and Spirituality

How do adolescents come to experience faith and spirituality? Griffith (2001) defines many stages of faith development and shows that adolescents come to this through identity shaping. Adolescents might shape their faith and spirituality through doubts and uncertainty, and they might try the different faith of their parents. This depends on good relations with the community they are surrounded with, including teachers and mentors.

Identity and social formation of identity is linked to the age of adolescence. Studies of Vygotsky done by Penuel and Wertsch (1995) state that understanding adolescence must be linked with identity formation. Like Erikson (1968), these

studies state that the function of adolescence is to discover identity standards and to select from those standards what is truly crucial for one's life. Erikson affirms the role of the context and environment in shaping identity, through his eight stages of development. According to him, adolescents do shape their identities through specific reactions and interactions to the community and the social environment.

Penuel and Wertsch (1995) agree with the importance of the role of teachers in schools in confirming identity. Teachers are bearers of the needed standards for the future. They are called on to be informative to evaluate personal development. They need to develop a reciprocal relationship with students, especially at schools. Teachers can influence students' achievements through their involvement in their motivation for learning. The authors advise teachers to follow two ways to a healthy, true, practical, authentic identity. When teachers go beyond encouraging to inspire identity modeling, and when they are ready to be a tool of transformation, then they can be this effective tool. Teachers are called on to create classrooms where students can find options and roads to success and change.

Aldridge and Ala'i (2013) and Fraser (2014) introduced the work of Lewin (1936), Murray (1978), and Stern (1970) when they affirm that there are contextual and situational factors in environments which have a role in behavioral differences. They even explain that the perceived environment and the needs of the persons are two factors that lead to shaping identity, character, and ultimately behavioral reactions. Positive school climates (teachers, peers, programs, and educational academic processes) are considered as important predictors for positive behavioral and emotional outcomes (Fraser, 2012; Anderson, Thomas, Moor, & Kool, 2008). Positive and improved teacher-student relationships improve discipline and order, and can lead to reduced behavioral complexities. Recognized values at school, even if not

recognized by their local communities, can be highly influential as well (Aldridge, & Ala'i, 2013). Teachers are crucial mediators in building not only students' identity, but also their spirituality.

Bryant (2008) argues that being in religious authority contexts will lead students in secular world to conceive a relative opinion about the superior, where knowledge is constructed by the knower only. However, "this stage of students' life will also lead to a liberated faith rather than naïve faith" (p. 4). He presents the work of Park where he finds that when young adults achieve this stage and rely on their own knowing, they are in great need for a community and spiritual mentors. Young adults are nurtured into being, and this happen through participating in a community that possesses a trust-worthy alternative to the previously assured knowledge. This means that young adults need to reform their previously structured knowledge of spirituality and God in a community that is able to offer convincing alternatives with reformed knowledge. Here, the role of the school climate, teachers, and peer interactions is needed. For Loder (1998), community can be a source of conformity or not, depending on its status quo. It might be either a source of freedom or a source of oppression. He presents this through saying that:

Adolescents behavior is a double-edged sword; what appears to be social nonconformity is often a dramatization of the undesired of large-scale social conformity. The greater danger to the human spirit in this is not from the adolescent side but from the sociocultural side: the fear of nonconformity on the part of status quo society will not so much redirect or transform the human spirit, but, if possible, suppress or break it so it will conform without complaint. (p. 205)

Loder (1998) presents the power of the spirit in being the liaison to transform the person's ego from oppression by sociocultural context to freedom with a vision.

Theories of faith development and formation of adolescent identity and spirituality reflect the importance of the environment, culture, and climate (Fowler, 1981; Fowler & Dell, 2005). Sheldrake (n.d.) also connects spirituality with context and interactions. For him, context is an essential element and hermeneutical framework in the modern study of spirituality. Spiritual experience is always linked with culture. Context is not something added to or subtracted from spiritual experience, but is the medium within which experiences take their forms and expressions. The role of the teacher and the school climate, in addition to culture and social contexts, are crucial in identity and spiritual conformity.

The important question emerging here is the kind of teachers one can think of for spiritual education. Fisher (1998) asserts that the nature and the belief of the teacher can enforce, enhance, or even restrict the development of students' spirituality. If schools want to enhance students' spirituality, they need to consider the issue of teachers' personal spiritual development. Adshead (as cited by Fisher (1998) writes:

When we replace the liberal Christian teacher by secular humanist teacher, implicit religious education becomes rapidly indistinguishable from personal and social education. Post Christian secular humanism is already emerging as the new spirituality in which any form of God-talk is an anachronism. (Fisher, 1998, p. 106)

Fisher (1998) presents what Adshead presented here about the characteristics of the new Christian teacher who is liberal. By liberal, he means a Christian who is ready to open spirituality to wide channels of reason and thinking, whereby religion is not the

target, but a way to be free from fatalism. By replacing this spiritual liberal teacher with a secular humanistic teacher, any talk of God could be considered as false talk. So what quality of Christian teacher is at stake here?

In '*Let us pray*'- *Diabolical liberty or educational opportunity?* McCaffry (1997) argues that prayer, which is a highly spiritual act, can be considered as educational opportunity where teachers do not impose their views of God on students. Prayers offer the freedom to explore the human spirit which is difficult to access in other ways. Prayers are further considered as creative work, especially when educators are not playing the role of God. Teachers thus nurture spirituality rather than regulate it. They should not instruct what to pray, but rather facilitate prayer as a tool of self-expression in front of God. Fisher advises teachers to understand the nature of the student who lacks trust and hope and looks for identity formation through relationships. Young learners look for ideals from different resources to build their spirituality and faith. Faith and spirituality are communal, and gaining them from spiritual liberal teachers might be more effective than secular resources, whereby morality and violence could be misleading. Teachers are called on to know what is contradictory and might lead to despair for students and adolescents, so they can know and plan their goals for building spiritually healthy students.

Is there a relation between spiritual education, Christian schools, and achievements? Wright (2016) presents the work of Godfrey (2008), Jeynes (2010), Regnerus (2003), Walker (2002), and Yokun (2010) in creating positive relationships between spiritual and religious education and achievement. Wright (2016) presents the relationship between intrinsic motivation that is supported by faith and the extrinsic motivation that is reflected in living high morals that might lead to achievements. He uses the theory of Erikson and others to assert that religious identity

depends on the parental and instructors' role in life. He argues that the role of teachers and peers in forming character and spirituality is highly recognized in all societies. Besides, teachers' education programs need to develop specific qualities in teachers to react to sensitivities of students' religions and spirituality. This role is even recognized in secular societies and communities (Ilkonen & Ubani, 2014; Rissanen, Kuusisto & Kuusisto, A. 2016; Poulter, & Riitaoja & Kuusisto, 2014; Kuusisto, Poulter & Kallioniemi, 2016).

Studying the climate of Christian schools and their role in students' life provide many positive results, contrary to what is recently believed by many writers, that Christian schools limit their students way of thinking and guide students towards pure religious laws and rituals (Smith, 2011). However, Wright (2016) presents the work done by Cardus researchers who discovered different outcomes for Catholics, Protestants, non-religious, and public schools with Protestant Christian school graduates. He states that "Graduates of Protestants Christian schools presented exemplary degrees of compliance, generosity, and outward-focus with a high commitment to God, church, family, and community" (Pennings, 2011, p. 45). The Cardus study lists three outcomes of Christian education: "spiritual formation, cultural engagement, and academic development" (p. 46). Moreover, researchers found that graduates of Protestant Christian schools exemplified a higher morale with positive values for the individual and the community (Pennings, 2011).

These positive research findings raise the question of why schools tend to lower the importance of spiritual or even liberal religious education. Paredes-Collins (2014) argues that some educational contexts fear the idea of spirituality because they speculate that spirituality may cover unpredictable agendas and may reflect a lower academic level. He adds that recently, some secular universities have shown an

interest in spirituality because of students' increased interest in these matters and lists the benefits of spirituality in colleges and schools based on research findings.

Students' spirituality can lead to more "college engagements, service involvement, leadership skills, and identification of life purpose, academic performance, psychological well-being, intellectual self-confidence, and satisfaction with school or college" (p. 172). Yet, Paredes-Collins (2014) observed that spirituality will not eliminate diversity.

Riggers-Piehl and Lehman (2016) describe the positive campus environment where students do not feel threatened to pursue spirituality. They state that research shows that "increasing engagement in aspects of spirituality in campus is associated with increase sense of belonging, sense of community, and satisfaction" (p. 248). They list the positive relation between students' spiritual life and students' ability. They find a correlation between meaningful life goals in tough times, the ability to achieve high academic performance, and activities related to a sense of belonging. In this sense they raise the question as to why someone would prefer to dampen and discourage religious and spiritual pursuits in schools and colleges. Riggers-Piehl and Lehman (2016) suggest that this is related to the confusion many feel over levels of freedom and constraints, as though related to the inability to expect the future agenda of spirituality in a secular world.

Regarding the issue of integrating spiritual or Christian education with a secular one, the problems cannot be solved by omitting one and retaining the other. We cannot deny that we are all living in a diverse world in which religion and spirituality play a crucial role. Denying its presence cannot present positive future results. Rissanen, Kuusisto and Kuusisto (2016) present a challenge to the idea of limiting religion or religious education to the private realm. They argue that teachers

who have no connections to religious ways cannot identify the needs of their religious students and their parents, and therefore cannot empathize with their needs and ambitions. In a diverse, polarized world, where schools are places for diversity, teachers must develop spiritual “sensitivity” to their students and their communities’ spiritualities and their identities. This kind of teacher preparation is for the sake of the preparation of a generation able to negotiate their religious faith with secular ones, and prepared to integrate and construct ideas using both.

What might result if spiritual or Christian liberal education are integrated into our schools’ curricula and programs? Ilkonen and Ubani (2014) present some problems teachers may face while incorporating spirituality into their educational curricula. The well-known one is confusing spiritual with moral. This will lead to another problem which is finding necessary strategies and instructions to implement spiritual and moral education. The inability to define spirituality and moral education has led many schools to omit their programs and limit them to specific actions or activities.

Finally, one cannot end this part without asserting that school climate can influence forming identity and spirituality in many ways. Teachers and their education are main factors in supporting adolescents into forming their identity and spirituality. Knowing the positive relation between school climate and students’ spirituality and omitting spiritual and Christian education from schools which are found in religious communities might not be a healthy solution. Moreover, schools are called on to open channels of communication whereby teachers and students can understand their spiritual needs, and thus be led to nurture them. What is needed from healthy schools is also needed from Evangelical schools, since it is known that these schools have had a pioneering role in building student identity and spirituality.

Evangelical School Climate and its Role in Student Spirituality

A clear observation of some Evangelical schools' missions and work in Lebanon on the field of students' spirituality and Christian formation introduced eager efforts to include spirituality at many levels. In this section I discuss the notes of some Evangelical school leaders and how they regard the challenges of their role in building and guiding students' spirituality.

Costa, a well-known Educational Evangelical leader and General Secretary of the Fellowship of the Evangelical Schools in Lebanon, reflects his fears saying: "Evangelical schools in Lebanon struggle to make tough choices regarding their priorities. Should the stronger emphasis be on education or faith, and how do we foster balanced growth of human soul, mind, and body in the lives of our students, Christian, and non-Christian?" (Costa, 2007, para. 1). He states that graduates of the Baptist Evangelical School in Beirut have no records of involvement in Lebanon's sectarian war, and this, he claims, relates to the impact of the Evangelical education at Baptist schools and other Evangelical schools. He emphasized that the impact of the school processes and works has touched teachers, students, and the whole school community of Muslims and Christians and ends by stating that the situation is now changing: with the increase in religious sectarian teaching, maintaining a Christian identity has been challenged and misunderstood. He ends with outlining the duties Evangelical schools continue to have and reaffirms that Evangelical schools, through their academic standards and reasonable costs, can win the hearts of both Christian and Muslim families, and can make their way to the hearts and the minds of the students. Evangelical schools can help students "build consensus, make peace, achieve reconciliation, appreciate diversity, accept differences, reject fanaticism, and above all accept and enjoy the love of God" (p. 1). Costa targets all aspects of the

school climate and outlines how Evangelical schools used to and must enhance a Christian identity.

Moreover, in a document on the Adventist education (n.d.) explains that “the restoration of human being to the image of their Maker through saving relationship with Jesus Christ, and the balance development of the whole person, are the educational ultimate purpose” (The Adventist School, n.d., para. 2). The Adventist School, in its document, made it clear that these schools follow an educationally sound curriculum that integrates faith with learning, promoting a healthy lifestyle.

Another respected statement was made by Awaad (2016), who is the Secretary of Educational and Pedagogical Affairs Committee of the National Evangelical Synod of Syria and Lebanon. Addressing the graduates of the Evangelical schools of Zahle and Beirut-Lebanon, he declared that graduates of these schools are graduates of schools which relate their identity to the person of Jesus Christ and his teachings about the perfect kingdom in the Bible. Evangelical schools translate this vision of preparing students through leading holistic education whereby students are able to succeed academically, with free and critical minds, balanced socially, psychologically and physically, aware of all environmental needs, and able to open bridges of acceptance with others in Lebanon. Awaad (2016) in this speech outlines the main dimensions of spirituality whereby students are able to look for valuable meanings in life through healthy orientation and connection to oneself, others, and the environment. He asserts that this is based on the teaching of Christ and his Kingdom. He concludes that this is the spirit and the spirituality of their (Evangelical Synod) schools (Awaad, 2016).

Evangelical schools historically have had a role in building students’ spirituality in addition to their pioneering role in learning as introduced in the first

chapter. The real challenge here is whether Evangelical schools can embody what these beliefs are. In a study done on the formation of religious identity and the role of religious schools, a positive correlation was found between religious identity formation and several characteristics of religious secondary schools. The process of formation and the presence of religious peers and adults, and the exposure to religious directions had a positive effect on the spirituality of secondary students (Wang, 2015; Francis, 2016). The question thus arises: are Evangelical schools looking for this mission? Evangelical schools are still leading schools with Christian mission statements whereby building students' character is inspired by Christian values, molded by Christian spirit, but yet, is this a spiritual education?

CHAPTER 3

METHOD

This study aims to examine students' perceptions of school climate and the spirituality in Evangelical schools in Lebanon. It aims also to examine the relationship between students' perception of Evangelical schools' climate and students' spirituality and observe if the climate in Evangelical schools correlates with students' spirituality. (Introduction part).

Design

The study utilizes a mixed methods design (Tashakkori & Teddlie, 2011). The data is collected with both quantitative and qualitative instruments. The rationale for this design relies on the concepts of perceptions and spirituality. Since the aim of the study is to examine the student perceptions in relation to school climate and their spirituality at Evangelical schools, the mixed methods design will introduce a wider understanding for the climate and spirituality of Evangelical schools. As mentioned in Chapter 2 about students' perceptions, it is also clearly stated by Fan, Williams and Corkin (2011) that "students' perceptions of school climate are not only associated with features of school climate within which students are situated, but also are shaped by their individual characteristics and experiences" (p. 2). The students' perceptions of school climate and spirituality may vary according to different internal psychological and emotional perceptions and understanding that might not relate directly to school climate or school in general. Therefore, data from the mixed

methods design (surveys, open ended questions, and interviews) here will provide “a powerful mix” (Miles & Habermas, 1994, p. 42) for examining the topic. The quantitative data will offer the needed information to examine both the students’ perceptions as a group of the school climate and spirituality, providing, for instance, an idea of how typical some views are among them. However, this data will not be enough to lead us to further examine if students’ spirituality is supported and enriched in school climate per se, or by other climates like home or special communities. Therefore, we need qualitative data that can lead us specifically to students’ perceptions of their specific school climate and its role in spirituality. These data are collected with open ended questions which are directed to the school climate and its role in spiritual formation, and from interviews with students from different ages and genders, attending different schools, as well as from interviews with responsible persons who plan, direct, and lead the spiritual life in the schools in question.

The design utilized in collecting and analyzing data represents Explanatory Sequential Design (Creswell, 2012). The quantitative data and results provide a general picture of the school climate and spirituality; more analysis, “especially through qualitative data collections is needed to refine, extend, and explain the general picture” (Creswell, 2012). The quantitative data is collected first, is introduced first in the study, and present a major aspect of school climate and spirituality at Evangelical schools. The qualitative data will follow in the second phase of the research. The qualitative data will be used to explain and highlight the main concerns of the research and will support the quantitative data. The qualitative data, the interviews, will follow the quantitative data.

The quantitative data survey includes two measures in the type of questionnaires, one that measures the school climate, and the other that measures

spirituality. To get specific answers from all participants in relation to school climate and spirituality, and in relation to their Evangelical schools' contexts, open-ended questions will be added at the end of the questionnaires. Open ended questions will include questions like: (1) what is the most influencing thing for you at school? And, (2) what does influence your spirituality at school?

The qualitative data set comprises two parts: (1) Interviews with students from each grade, separately and in groups. (2) Interviews with the person responsible of students' spiritual life. Interviews focus on questions related specifically to the school climate examined in concern of students' spirituality. Interviews with the person who directs spiritual life will focus on the programs and activities which his or her school lead to enrich the students' spirituality.

Participants

The study focused on four Evangelical schools in Lebanon, which are different in their demographics, Christian programs, and locations (Table 1). None of these schools were newly established, thus old in heritage and reputation as strong foundations for education in Lebanon. The research targeted high school students between Grades 7 and 12 (Ages 12-18), with one or two section/group of 20-40 students of each grade in each school. The paragraph below shows the needed information for each of the schools under study. The schools are identified by letters as school A, B, C, and D. The following paragraph provides an explanation of the schools' specific demographic, location, Christian and spiritual activities, academic programs and their varieties, and other varieties like school size, age of work, etc.

Table 1 presents the valid and representative sample of the number of participants in each school and their percentages. Tables 2, 3, and 4 present the valid number and percentages of participants according to gender, grade, and age.

Table 1

School of Participants

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	School A	144	25.0	25.0	25.0
	School B	119	20.6	20.6	45.6
	School C	186	32.2	32.2	77.8
	School D	128	22.2	22.2	100.0
	Total	577	100.0	100.0	

Table 2

Gender of Participants

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	301	52.2	52.8	52.8
	Female	269	46.6	47.2	100.0
	Total	570	98.8	100.0	
Missing	System	7	1.2		
Total		577	100.0		

Table 3

Grade of Participants

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Grade 7	147	25.5	25.7	25.7
	Grade 8	105	18.2	18.3	44.0
	Grade 9	96	16.6	16.8	60.7
	Grade 10	107	18.5	18.7	79.4
	Grade 11	79	13.7	13.8	93.2
	Grade 12	39	6.8	6.8	100.0
	Total	573	99.3	100.0	
Missing	System	4	.7		
Total		577	100.0		

Table 4

Age of Participants

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	11	2	.3	.4	.4
	12	83	14.4	14.9	15.2
	13	109	18.9	19.5	34.8
	14	112	19.4	20.1	54.8
	15	91	15.8	16.3	71.1
	16	86	14.9	15.4	86.6
	17	55	9.5	9.9	96.4
	18	19	3.3	3.4	99.8
	19	1	.2	.2	100.0
Total		558	96.7	100.0	
Missing	System	19	3.3		
Total		577	100.0		

Both school climate and SHALOM 2 surveys, used in this study, were tested by SPSS program for reliability. Cronbach's Alfa scale for school climate survey scaled $r = 0.9$ and for spirituality scaled $r = 0.921$. Both surveys reflected high reliability scales.

Description of Schools that Participated in the Study

The schools age of work in education varies between 150-60 years of work. The total number of the school students also varies, school A has more than 900 students, K-12 where schools B, C, and D have 500-700 students, K-12. The schools also vary in their academic programs where schools A, B, C, and D have both Lebanese and American programs, where school B only have, beside other programs, special Education program with inclusion orientation. All of the schools present good academic levels of learning. This is witnessed in the 99-100% of their students' success in national standardized testing. Schools differ in their character building programs where A pioneers in different character building programs with focus on leadership awareness, beside other occasional ones; schools B and D have occasional charter programs for some classes and ages, where school C do not offer character programs at all, all ethical programs are directed in daily life processes. For Christian Education curriculum and spiritual religious life, schools also do vary. School A, B, and D do offer chapels for students on weekly basis with variance of attendance. Schools A, B, and D give Bible classes and Christian Education hours on weekly basis, however, school A offer this only to Grades 7-9 where B offers this to grades 7-12, and D only up to Grade 7. School C do not offer at all any Christian education or Bible lessons to grades 7-12 and Christian education hours are supported only to lower ages. All schools present prayers led by pastors or religious leaders at official events like graduation and other ceremonies. The demographics of schools

also vary between religions and sociocultural backgrounds of their students. Students of the schools, A and B are majority of Christians where students of school A belong to different sociocultural backgrounds of school B. Schools C and D have more than 50-60% of their students from Muslim backgrounds, where schools, A and B have less than 30-40 families of Muslim religion. Schools A and B are in Beirut city where schools, C and D are located in the suburbs of Beirut. Schools facilities and physical appearance differs too. School A and D have larger campuses than schools, B and C. School A and D have sports programs with varsity teams, where schools, B and C are limiting their sports programs to weekly hours during school time. Schools A, B, C, and D do not offer music or art sessions or weekly hours to their students. School A and B have active drama shows for Grades 10-11. School A offers drama hours on weekly basis. All schools do not offer regular extra-curricular program for their students, only school A have recognized sports as one of them. All schools have their students participate in community services, yet all of them have it on occasional basis and for some classes only.

Data Collection Process, Analysis, and Triangulation

Data is analyzed to answer the main questions of this research: (1) What is the school climate? (2) What are the students' perceptions of school climate? (ASSC instrument survey and interviews) (3) What is spirituality? (4) What are the students' perceptions of spirituality (SHALOM 2 instrument)? (5) What is the relation between students' perception of school climate and spirituality (Correlation)?

Perceptions of school climate and spirituality were considered in relation to grades 7-12 or ages from 12-18 years, gender, and in total. The independent variables are age, grade, and gender and the dependent ones are schools A, B, C, and D.

ANOVA is used to analyze variables like ages and grades in the same school and

between different schools, and school climate and spirituality. Correlation between students' perception of school climate and spirituality is analyzed. Correlation does not mean here causation. The aim of the research is not to prove what causes or influences the spirituality of the students at Evangelical schools. Correlation here is to consider and describe the role and the coloration possibility between students' perception of schools' climate and their spirituality. Correlation analysis will lead us to understand the relationship between students' perceptions of their own school climate and spirituality and the possible positive or negative connection between them. The SPSS program is used to analyze data.

Data collection process started with students in Evangelical schools. No order of schools was offered here to start with the data collection process. Students at each school were given a brief introduction about the research and its aim, and are introduced to the meaning of the main topics of the research which are climate and spirituality. Students were encouraged to answer questions individually and according to their own experience at school. Assistance was given only when students faced difficult English words. The surveys were presented in the English language, since English is the language used in most of the programs at Evangelical schools. In most of the schools, survey took about 25-30 minutes to fill out.

Following the surveys, students were asked to participate in specific oral interviews upon their own acceptance. Most of the schools' students stated their willingness to participate, however, only 4-5 students were encouraged to join. Interviews with a staff member working for the students' spiritual health were assigned either after students' interviews or at an arranged time.

Data analysis follows the mentioned design of Explanatory Sequential Design. The data collected from the two surveys were presented and analyzed first followed

by qualitative data to support the first analysis. Triangulation of data here means summarizing and ‘putting into dialogue’ the results of the three processes of data collections at the end for the following aims: (1) the issues of spirituality and school climate perceptions are relative; a concentration on the case of schools’ role to spirituality is needed. (2) We needed to make sure that students’ experience of spirituality is narrowed to schools only, since some students reflected high spiritual experience while interviewed and some were not. (3) We will be able to draw more comprehensive picture to the case of Evangelical schools studied. (4) To assure the validity of the instruments used to the context of Evangelical schools in Lebanon.

Instruments

The aim of the instruments is to: (1) examine the schools’ climate (students’ perceptions), (2), examine students’ spirituality, (3) examine possible correlation between both, and (4) examine what spirituality is like at Evangelical schools. The two quantitative surveys will focus on students’ perceptions of their school climate and spirituality. The qualitative surveys (interviews) will focus on what students’ perceptions are like about the climate and spirituality in the Evangelical schools examined.

The climate survey used in this study is the *School Climate Quality Analytic Assessment Instrument*, developed by the Alliance for the Study of School Climate (2016). It is used here with 6 dimensions distributed to cover 56 questions dealing with secondary students’ perceptions. The 6 dimensions are: (1) physical appearance (8 questions), (2) students’ interactions (10 questions), (3) discipline and management environment (10 questions), (4) learning instructions and assessments (11 questions), (5) attitude and culture (10 questions), (6) community relations (7 questions) (ASSC SCAI-S-S Instrument v. 2016 7.4.0). “The climate instrument follows analytic trait

structure. This design provides the survey participants with three options that represent levels of phenomena between high, middle, and low and in between options of high-middle and middle-low (1 is High, 2 is high-middle, 3 is middle, 4 is middle-low, and 5 is low). Item options represent the range levels of institutional function, quality of practice and/or the experience of the participant at the school” (Schindler, 2016, P.1). Studies of school climates tools and surveys showed that this survey done by the *Alliance for the Study of School Climate* is reliable. In practice, The ASSC demonstrates exceptionally high levels of reliability as measured by the Cronbach’s Alpha test (0.97). The accepted standard for a reliable instrument is (0.7) (Clifford. et al. 2012). Studies of this instrument revealed that “Psychology of Success” is integrated into items as conceptual definitions versus “Psychology of failure” (p. 3). This instrument also can reflect a complete picture of overall school climate and function given its eight dimensions and multiple sub-scales. Another positive factor to this instrument is its capability of achieving high levels of correlation with student achievement (p. 5). Schindler also explains that this instrument can reflect the phenomena and its real problems vs. symptoms. The Alliance for Studying School Climate granted permission to use this instrument and all needed files. (Permission is granted through mail with specific link to use for data collection (Appendix A-C).

The spirituality survey is the survey of John Fisher for spiritual well-being called SHALOM2 (Fisher, 2010). The spirituality instrument covers 20 questions related to 4 dimensions of spirituality. The first dimension is the personal, the second is the communal, the third is the transcendent, and the last is the natural. Question of personal spiritual wellbeing are items 5, 9, 14, 16, 18; communal spiritual wellbeing items are 1, 3, 8, 17, 19; environmental spiritual wellbeing items are 4, 7, 10, 12, 20; and Transcendental spiritual wellbeing items are 2, 6, 11, 13, 15. The spirituality

survey SHALOM2 uses double response techniques or domains of examining spiritual wellbeing. The first is about the ideal expectation of spiritual health, and the second is about how students feel about it at their school. The aim of the double-response technique is to compare the “lived experience” with their “ideals” for spiritual wellbeing. “This fairer approach, as Fisher (2016) explained, is to assess spiritual well-being as it has shown the difference in scores between the “ideals” and “lived experiences,” called “spiritual harmony/dissonance,” provides a statistically stronger measure than using only “lived experience” which is what measures employ” (p. 8). Fisher (1999) reported in a study presented about SHALOM to students of different ages and years and schools that “the two 20-item sections of SHALOM scored high internal consistency, with Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measures of Sampling Adequacy (KMO) of .925-.907” (p. 10). The four sets of five items were examined for reliability as subscales and were found to have KMO values ranging from .70 to .89 which are acceptable levels indicating reliability of SHALOM 2 tool. The spirituality instrument follows Likert scale of numbers between very low, low, moderate, high, and very high (5 is very low, 4 is low, 3 is middle, 2 is high, and 1 is very high). The aim of this instrument is to examine students’ perceptions of their spirituality and how they ideal it. Permission to use this instrument is given by John Fisher through mail conversation personally with him (Appendix A-C). The instrument has been used in many studies and many researchers’ works.

At the introduction of the two instruments, the students cover information about their class, and gender. Schools will be addressed under alphabetical letters (explained in the participants’ part). At the beginning of the two surveys, students were asked voluntarily to answer two open ended questions like: (1) What is the most influencing thing for you at school? And, (2) What influences your spirituality at

school? The aim of these two open ended questions was to collect students' perceptions of their specific school and spirituality in relation to their own school (Aim is mentioned also in the rationale of the mixed method design).

The interviews addressed two parts: (1) open-ended interviews with students from G7-12 girls and boys ages between 12-18 in groups and separately; the duration of these interviews varied between 15-20 minutes. (2) Interviews with persons responsible or offices for students' spiritual life at schools; the aim of this interviews was to examine what spirituality and school climate are at the Evangelical school examined. The duration of this interview was 10-11 minutes. The spiritual life leader was asked to answer the questions orally or written as preferred. The data collected from interviews were analyzed after collecting the quantitative data. Open-ended interviews with students addressed possible 2-3 students from each grade or age group on a voluntary basis and during their recess times (Appendix B).

Ethical Considerations

School administrations received a letter that explains the aim of the study and permission to conduct the research with their students. The letter clarified the process of data collection. The permission included the possible time and duration of collecting data and leading the process.

The individual and group interviews were respected, and students' information were used here only in a way that does not harass or hurt the school or the individual. Personal views were not shared in public, and anonymity of interviewee was highly considered and respected. The name of the schools were not titled in all processes since it is not part of the aim of the project and neither the specific demography or gender or religious background of the students.

Even if complete anonymity might be impossible for the researcher, confidentiality was ensured. Data collection did not target participants' personal life issues and experiences outside the topic area. Participants were asked to answer questionnaires according to their will and voluntary role after or before getting involved in. Individual answers from survey data were highlighted and all findings were reported anonymously. The reporting of the survey data was only in aggregate as group answers. Comparison between schools were not done in ways that harass schools' identities or efforts. Comparisons were done in recognized positive correlation possibilities between schools' climates and spirituality and their subscales.

CHAPTER 4

RESULTS

The aim of this chapter is to address the main purpose statement and answer the research questions of this study as addressed in the introduction. This chapter presents the students' perceptions of both school climate and spirituality at Evangelical schools in Lebanon, and the possible correlation between these two. First, the main descriptive statistics of the two surveys with means and standard deviations are presented. This aims to describe how students perceived both, the school climate and spiritual health of their own schools. Second, the results of ANOVA are presented, highlighting what is significant. Third, possible correlations are studied between the two independent variables: school climate and spiritual health or spirituality. Fourth, the linear regression between school climate as the independent variable and the state of feeling of spirituality as the dependent one are presented. The discussion following this part is to highlight the main ideas and results in relation to what was presented about them in the literature review and to pinpoint and interpret important findings.

Statistical Results

Students in all schools A, B, C, D, perceived that their school climate and spirituality at their schools were both moderate to high (see Tables 5 and 6). A total of 573 students from all schools perceived that their school climates and the physical appearance of their schools was middle-high ($M = 2.35$, $SD = 0.67$) (note that 1 is high and 5 is low). Students in all schools perceived their school climates with all

their subscales as middle-high with close means and standard deviations (see Table 5). However, students perceived the schools' community relations ($M = 2.29$, $SD = 0.78$) more positively than any of the other aspects of the school. All students' perceptions of their school climate were similar, both within and across schools (SD ranges from 0.66 to 0.84). In general, students in all schools perceived their school climate as middle-high ($M = 2.45$, $SD = 0.65$) (see Table 7).

Table 5

Students' Perceptions of School Climate with Subscales

	Physical appearance	Student interaction	Discipline environment	Learning assessment	Attitude and culture	Community relation
Valid	573	574	575	573	568	562
Missing	4	3	2	4	9	15
Mean	2.35	2.48	2.51	2.47	2.52	2.29
SD	.67	.66	.75	.84	.82	.78

The spirituality survey used in this study has two parts. One is related to students' perceptions of the ideal state of spirituality, and another part was for how spirituality or spiritual health is perceived at school. This survey also follows a Likert scale, with 1 as very high, 2 as high, and 3 as moderate, 4 as low, and 5 as very low. The survey included 4 domains of spirituality: The Divine, others, oneself, and nature. The students perceived their ideal state of spirituality within themselves as high ($M = 2$, $SD = 0.77$), however, their perception of their actual state of personal spirituality was lower ($M = 2$, $SD = 0.77$) (see Table 6). Students from all schools perceived their ideal state with God ($M = 1.86$, $SD = 0.92$) as higher than what they feel at schools

($M = 2.7$, $SD = 0.93$). Students from all schools perceived their ideal state of spirituality with nature as higher ($M = 2.31$, $SD = 0.85$) than what they felt of their spirituality in relation to nature at school ($M = 2.74$, $SD = 0.98$). Students from all schools also perceived their ideal state of spirituality with others as higher ($M = 2.01$, $SD = 0.79$) than what they felt their actual spirituality was in relation to others at schools ($M = 2.36$, $SD = 0.78$) (see Table 6). At all schools, students perceived and reflected that their ideal state of spirituality with God, nature, others, and oneself as higher ($M = 2.04$, $SD = 0.66$) than what they felt of their spirituality at schools ($M = 2.56$, $SD = 0.68$) (see Table 7).

Students in all schools felt that their spirituality at school was moderate. They felt that what they felt regarding their sense of identity, self-awareness, joy, inner peace, and meaningful life as moderate. They felt their spirituality at schools regarding a relation with God, peace with God, oneness with God, and worship of God the Creator as moderate. Students from all schools felt their spirituality at schools regarding relation with nature, oneness with nature, harmony with it, feeling of awe and breathtaking as moderate. They also felt their spirituality at school regarding relations with others, loving them, respecting them, and forgiving them as moderate (see Table 6). However, students in all schools perceived that their ideal state of spirituality with its four domains higher than what they feel about spirituality at school in all four domains (see Tables 6 and 7).

Table 6

Students' Perceptions of Spiritual Health/ Spirituality with Subscales

	Ideal State of SH with oneself	Ideal state of SH with God	Ideal state of SH with nature	Ideal state of SH with others	State of feeling with oneself	State of feeling with God	State of feeling with nature	State of feeling with others
Valid	560	562	561	563	560	563	557	564
Missing	17	15	16	14	17	14	20	13
Mean	2.00	1.86	2.31	2.01	2.36	2.7	2.74	2.44
Std. Deviation	.77	.92	.85	.79	.78	.93	.98	.84

Table 7

Students Perceptions of School Climate and Spirituality

	School climate	State of feeling of SH	Ideal State of SH
N	Valid	576	564
	Missing	1	13
Mean		2.45	2.56
Std. Deviation		.65	.68

Is there a difference between what male and female students perceive as ideal and feel of their spirituality at schools? Descriptive gender data on spirituality presents that female ideal states of spirituality are slightly higher than males with mean of 1.98 for females and 2.09 for males and same standard deviation for both of 0.66. Yet, there were no differences in what they felt about their spirituality at schools (see Table 8).

Table 8

Student Perceptions of Spiritual Health by Gender

Gender	Number		Mean		Std. Deviation	
	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female
Ideal State of spirituality	292	264	2.09	1.98	.66	.66
State of feeling of Spirituality	292	265	2.57	2.56	.68	.69

Although schools differ in their location and demography, programs and activities, students in all schools perceived their school climate with all their descriptions and subscales—the physical appearance, the discipline environment, interaction, learning and assessments, attitudes and culture, and community relations—as middle-high. Means ranged between 2.34 in school B with standard deviation of 0.76 to 2.59 in school A with a standard deviation of 0.58 (see Table 9).

However, perceptions of spirituality were not similar in all schools (see Table 10). Descriptive data showed that students of school B perceived their ideal state of spirituality at their school as being slightly higher than what students of schools A, C, and D perceived with a mean of 1.86 and a standard deviation of 0.61. Yet, students in all schools were relatively similar in what they perceived spirituality was like at their schools (see Table 10).

Table 9

Descriptive Statistics of School Climate by Schools

	School A			School B			School C			School D		
	N	Mean	SD									
School climate	144	2.59	.58	118	2.34	.76	186	2.46	.60	128	2.37	.63
Physical appearance	143	2.43	.56	118	2.16	.74	186	2.34	.66	126	2.44	.70
Students interactions	144	2.69	.64	118	2.38	.71	186	2.45	.65	126	2.39	.60
Discipline environment	144	2.71	.73	118	2.41	.83	186	2.51	.67	127	2.37	.75
Learning assessment	144	2.65	.79	117	2.33	.95	186	2.47	.78	126	2.40	.84
Attitude and culture	144	2.64	.74	115	2.48	.95	184	2.57	.79	125	2.36	.78
Community relations	144	2.26	.67	112	2.18	.89	185	2.45	.77	121	2.18	.79

Table 10

Descriptive Statistics of Spirituality by Schools

	School A			School B			School C			School D		
	N	M	SD	N	M	SD	N	M	SD	N	M	SD
Ideal state of spirituality	143	2.08	.64	113	1.86	.61	184	2.01	.61	123	2.21	.75
State of feeling of spirituality	142	2.47	.55	114	2.57	.78	185	2.68	.70	123	2.49	.66
Ideal, spirituality with oneself	143	2.08	.72	111	1.83	.73	184	1.92	.76	122	2.19	.81
Ideal, spirituality with God	143	1.73	.80	112	1.70	.87	184	1.96	1.00	123	2.02	.93
Ideal, spirituality with nature	143	2.35	.78	111	2.05	.82	184	2.32	.85	123	2.47	.92
Ideal, spirituality with others	143	2.19	.80	113	1.85	.72	184	1.85	.72	123	2.18	.85
Feeling, spirituality with oneself	142	2.26	.70	112	2.47	.84	184	2.44	.81	122	2.25	.72
Feeling spirituality with God	142	2.43	.61	113	2.62	.96	185	2.95	1.05	123	2.73	.94
Feeling, spirituality with nature	142	2.64	.86	111	2.72	1.21	183	2.92	.96	121	2.60	.89
Feeling spirituality with others	142	2.53	.80	114	2.41	.86	185	2.42	.86	123	2.38	.84

ANOVA, Post-hoc Analysis

Univariate analysis (ANOVA) was conducted to determine if students' perceptions of school climate, students' spirituality (ideal), students' spirituality (state of feeling) and total spirituality differed according to gender, grade or school. The state of feeling as it related to spiritual health differed significantly according to school, $F(3, 504) = 4.008, p = .008$ and grade, $F(5, 504) = 7.601, p < .001$. Tukey post-hoc analysis revealed that the state of feeling of spirituality was significantly higher in school C than schools A ($p = .019$) and D ($p = .03$) (see Table D2, Appendix D).

Total spirituality also significantly differed according to grade, $F(5, 504) = 4.653, p < .01$. Grade 7 students were significantly less positive in their overall spiritual health than grades 10, 11 and 12 (all $p < .01$). Furthermore, males and females differed on their ideal perception of spirituality where female students were higher than male students, $F(1, 504) = 5.284, p = .022$ (see Table D3, Appendix D, and Table 8).

Tukey post hoc analysis indicated that students' perceptions about the school climate in School A were significantly more positive than in school B ($p < .01$) and school D ($p < .01$). However, there was no indication of significant differences in students' perceptions of spiritual health by schools (Table D2, Appendix D).

Correlations

Correlation analysis revealed a positive correlation between students' perceptions of school climate and spiritual health at Evangelical schools (Pearson's $r(n = 564) = .45, p < .001$) (see Table 11).

Table 11

Correlation between Student Perceptions of School Climate and Spirituality

		Spiritual Health
School climate	Pearson Correlation	.459**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	<i>N</i>	564

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

A positive correlation between students' perceptions of school climate and feeling spiritual at schools was found in all schools. Correlation was presented here by school climate and all its subscales, and with spirituality and its two parts, the ideal and state of feeling. All school climate subscales in all schools correlate with students' spirituality, the ideal and what they feel. The strongest correlation was reflected between school climate and schools' community relations and students feeling of spirituality at schools (Pearson's $r (n = 448) = .511, p < .01$). Community relations and how schools related and enforced relations to surrounding communities and involved with them correlated positively with what students of all schools felt of their spirituality. Enforcing community relations will correlate positively with students' spirituality at schools (see Table 12).

Since schools have different programs and activities with students from different demographic and socioeconomic backgrounds, presenting correlations by schools can be helpful and informative. Higher scores in spirituality were associated with higher scores on the school climate instrument. A positive correlation between school climate and spirituality was found in all schools. Yet, this correlation was strongest in School C (Pearson's $r (n = 185) = .532, p < .001$) (see Table 13).

Table 12

Correlation between School Climate and Spirituality by Subscales

		Ideal State of SH	State of feeling of SH
Physical appearance	Pearson Correlation	.217**	.387**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000
	N	559	560
Student interaction	Pearson Correlation	.168**	.379**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000
	N	560	561
Discipline environment	Pearson Correlation	.187**	.418**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000
	N	561	562
Learning assessment	Pearson Correlation	.240**	.431**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000
	N	560	561
Attitude and culture	Pearson Correlation	.191**	.484**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000
	N	558	559
Community relation	Pearson Correlation	.200**	.511**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000
	N	557	558

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 13

Correlation between Student Perceptions of School Climate and Spirituality by Schools

	School A	School B	School C	School D
Pearson Correlation	.330**	.476**	.532**	.489**
Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000
N	143	113	185	123

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

A positive correlation was found by gender between students' perceptions of school climate and spirituality (see Table 14). Both males' and females' perceptions of their school climate correlated with their ideal state of spirituality and what they felt at school. However, higher scores of correlations of what females felt (Pearson's $(n = 265) r = 0.556, p < .01$) of their spirituality were found with what they perceived of their school climate in all schools than what males in all schools felt and perceived (Pearson's $r (n = 291) = .462, p < .01$). Females had a stronger relationship between what spirituality should be and felt with school climate than what males had (see Table 14).

Table 14

Correlation between Perceptions of School Climate and Spirituality by Gender

		Male		Female	
		Ideal state of SH	State of feeling of SH	Ideal state of SH	State of feeling of SH
School climate	Pearson's Correlation	.315**	.462**	.162**	.556**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.009	.000
	N	291	291	264	265

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). SH = Spiritual Health

Regression

A linear regression was used to determine the effect of students' perceptions of school climate on the state of feeling of spiritual health at school. Visual inspection of a plot of standardized residuals compared to standardized predicted values showed homoscedasticity (Figures 1 and Figures D1 and D2, and Tables D4, D5, and D6, Appendix D). Similarly, examination of the p-p plot of residuals showed that the data was normally distributed.

Average students' perceptions of school climate significantly predicted the state of feeling of spirituality at schools, $F(1, 562) = 193.449$, $p < 0.001$, accounting for 25.6% of the variation in the state of feeling of spirituality, with adjusted $R^2 = 25.5\%$. The prediction equation was: state of feeling of Spirituality = $1.255 + 0.535 * \text{school climate}$ (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Regression p –p plot graph of school climate and spirituality.

The null hypothesis is that school climate and the learning environment have no correlation with students' spirituality and do not reflect students' spirituality. If this null hypothesis is true then, in Evangelical schools, the programs and activities, academics, curricula, student-teacher interactions, and schools' psychological and physical settings would not correlate with students' spirituality. The regression statistical results too show that this null hypothesis should be rejected.

Qualitative Data

The qualitative data for this study consists of two parts: the open-ended questions addressed to all students about their school climate and spirituality, and the interviews with students and individuals responsible for spiritual life or related domains in the schools under study. The aim of this data is to clarify and explain the results from the quantitative data about school climate and spirituality.

Open Ended Questions

The summary of the answers of the two open-ended survey questions is presented in the following tables. When students were asked what affected them the most in schools, most of them highlighted the importance of interactions with students (36-44%) and with teachers (17.6-27%). Students in most of the schools also highlighted the role of academics and learning assessments (grades) in their school climate (11-24%). Even in some schools, students saw this issue of grades as more influential than their relationships with their teachers (see Table 15).

Students in all schools were asked to answer a question related to their spirituality and what affected their spirituality the most (see Table 16). Most of the them perceived that they are spiritually influenced by their schools. In all schools,

again, interactions with friends had a significant role in raising and influencing their spirituality and in some schools, interactions with teachers were also important. In schools A, B, and D, students reflected that their relationship with God in school affected their spirituality, whereas students in school C said that only a small percentage (2.8%) felt that relations with God, Chapels, and Bible studies affected their spirituality. This can be explained because school C does not have Christian education programs or any Bible studies, chapels, or worship times for their students. Perhaps because of this, students of school C found that their own identity and their understanding of their own selves affected their spirituality the most (15.7%). Students in school C as in all the other schools, also highlighted the interaction factor in their spirituality at their school and this also affirmed that they do feel spiritual even though Christian programs were not explicitly part of the curriculum (see Table 16).

Summaries of the open-ended questions supported the quantitative data and descriptive data about school climate and spirituality that were presented in Tables 5, 6, and 7 about the students' perceptions of their school climate and spirituality at their school. Relations and interactions were considered as necessary factors for both. Spirituality at schools does not only depend on Christian education programs and religious education, yet many factors intervene together, mainly interactions with the whole school community and culture.

Table 15

What Affects the Students the Most at Their Schools?

Descriptions	A	B	C	D
Number of answers for Q.1	187	154	247	176
Physical Appearance	4.8%	8.4%	13.7%	10.7%
Interactions with friends	34.7%	44.80%	36.8%	37.5%
Interactions with Teachers	27.2%	23.3%	21.4%	17.6%
Grades	24%	11.6%	16.1%	18.7%
Good education	5.3%	-	6.8%	6.8%
Activities	1.60%	-	-	8.5%
Programs	2.4%	-	2.8%	-
Strict rules	-	11.6%	2.8%	-

Table 16

What Affects Spirituality the Most at School?

Descriptions	A	B	C	D
Number of answers	153	121	178	174
Relating to God, Chapels, Bible sessions	27.4%	28.9%	2.8%	16.6%
Interaction with friends	33.3%	20.6%	36.8%	31.6%
Interactions with Teachers	10.4%	5.78%	28.65%	23.5%
Spiritual relation to oneself	6.53%	7.4%	15.7%	8.6%
The role of school nature and environment	3.9%	7.4%	5.6%	5.7%
Activities (Trips, outings, art, music, dance, etc.)		7.4%	3.9%	5.7%
Nothing	-	22.3%	-	8%

Interviews

Both, students and responsible leaders for students' spirituality were interviewed. Students were asked after filling out the surveys to voluntarily join and meet for interviews. Some students did not feel comfortable leaving their classrooms and joining the interviews, therefore, in some classes, all the students in the class were asked to stay and feel free to answer. In all schools, male and female students from all the age groups under study were asked questions related to their school's climate and spirituality. The aim of all these questions was to clarify how students perceived their spirituality and school climate. Other interviews were conducted with persons who are responsible and leaders for spiritual life, and in some schools the head of the school or heads of sections were interviewed. Summarized interviews with students from different schools present the points below.

School culture and interactions. Students described that school culture and the way students treat each other is the most important factor in spiritual life and school climate. This also supports the descriptive data we had about what students perceived about their school's climate (see Tables 5, 6, 7 and Tables 15, 16). Students in all schools perceived that their interactions with each other and with their teachers elevates the quality of their life at their schools. For example, a student reflected that:

My school is an amazing school, although we don't have many programs, yet I feel I belong to a real family. The culture and the way we treat each other is so relaxing. (School D/ Grade 11/ personal interview/April 2017)

Good academics. Most of the students were convinced that their school's academic level was good, and this is one of the things that made them come to Evangelical schools. Evangelical schools are perceived as being good centers for good academics and education, and not only in Lebanon (Awaad, 2016; Costa, 2007).

Again, this is like the descriptive data presented in Tables 5, 6, 7 and 9. A student from grade 10 explained:

My family and I are convinced that I am in a good school where learning here can guarantee me university approval. Although I am not a Christian, I believe learning in this school can present me high academics. (School C, Grade 10, personal interview, April 2017)

Schools have a role in spirituality. Students believe that their schools had a role in their spirituality, yet they did not fully live up to their expectations. Although Evangelical schools have strong academic levels, students felt that the amount of testing and homework were stressing and a source of worry. Most researchers highlighted the need for interaction and relations as an important factor beside academics to live and feel spiritual at schools (Fisher, 2009; Loukas, 2007; Tubbs & Garner, 2008). One of the students in grade 10 expressed that:

Although the school is offering us good academics, we are so stressed. We don't have time to express ourselves and what we want and dream of. We don't have time to think of ourselves and how we feel towards God or others. (School B, Grade 10, personal interview, May 2017)

And another student from grade 9 said:

Lessons are so strict and heavy, and we have to study most of the time. (School A, Grade 9, personal interview, March 2017)

Students were asking for a chance to enrich their social and spiritual interactions beside their academics. Schools in this manner are challenged to enrich both the academic and the interaction programs without affecting negatively anyone of them. One of the best ways to work on this tension, is to involve students in planning their

spiritual and social interactions without influencing their academics. This might also encourage their positive interactions and elevate the quality of life at school.

Traditional Bible lessons are not enough. Most of the students at schools highlighted that the source of being spiritual is related to teachers and students' good and positive interactions more than religious programs. Although schools, A and B, students mentioned that chapels and Christian program are helping, but not enough and are limited to short times or to traditional Bible lessons.

Chapels are one of our good times to talk about God, but they are limited to very short times and we don't have access to [the] chapel hall to sit and pray.

(School A, grade 11, personal interview, March 2017)

Students in school B expressed their need to have open talks about God other than traditional Bible lessons, and open ways of talking about religious life that relate to their daily life activities.

The Bible lessons we have are good, but are not challenging us as young people and they are presenting only the religious point of view of our school religiosity. (School B, grade 10, personal interview, May 2017)

In school C, students expressed their need to have open sessions and talks where they can discuss different life issue and talks, even when these talks mean talking about God to Muslim students in Evangelical schools.

We love to have sessions where we can discuss existential issues, like who is God and is he real. We know we are not Christians, but we have to discuss these issues in our classes with all teachers. (School C, grade 12, personal interview, April 2017)

Planned programs for the environment and nature. Students did not see any planned programs in their schools about the environment or nature. When students were asked about their relationship with nature, they assured me that:

We love nature and we love to have green areas in our schools. We love to sit and relax under green trees, yet, we don't have. The school is taking us to outing and trips once or twice a year only. (School B, grade 8, personal interview, May 2017)

Students do care about nature and they collected money and raised them to plant trees in their school surrounding, but the project stopped, and plans are stopped for academic reasons. (School D, personal interview, April 2017)

One of the domains Fisher (1998) presented about spirituality is having a relationship with nature. Being separated from nature cannot present a holistic approach to spirituality. Supporting students with moments with nature, and presenting programs that encourage students to mediate and reflect will elevate their spirituality and therefore their feeling spiritual at schools (Wright, 2016; Loder, 1998; Griffith, 2001).

Feeling safe and accepted. Most of the students at all schools felt safe and accepted by their teachers and peers. A student expressed this idea by saying:

I have never felt I am a Muslim or stranger. My school loves me, and all my teachers and friends accept me as I am. (School D, grade 7, personal interview, April 2017)

Feeling accepted and emotionally stable and relaxed at schools proved that can elevate the work of students and their achievement. Students with high feelings of self-belonging and identity can prove better academic achievements and positive interactions (Cohen, Pickeral & McCloskey, 2009).

Summarized interviews with persons responsible for student life at the schools presented the following ideas.

Spirituality is needed at schools. All interviewees expressed their interest in their students' spiritual life at schools. One of the heads of sections said:

Our target is to deal with the students as a whole. We do care about their spirituality as other needs. We try our best to integrate many activities to our academics and help them feel spiritually relaxed. (School C, head of section, personal interview, April 2017)

Positive relations are crucial too. All interviewees asserted that they do care to build positive relations with their students where students feel satisfied and accepted. Many students during interviews asserted also their positive relations with most of their teachers and principals. One of the schools' principals reflected saying:

I do care to talk to students and invite them to my office and listen to their needs and try my best to respond and help. (School C, head of section – high school, personal discussion, April 2017)

We lack programs of spiritual education. Most of the interviewees reflected that there are no clear plans or programs for spiritual education other than Christian programs that are limited to chapels and Christian education Bible lessons. We can say that there is a kind of misunderstanding of what spirituality is. Most of the interviewees presented their understanding of spirituality as religiosity.

We thought by offering chapels and Christian education classes, students are getting more spiritual, and we are trying to do our best with the help of church leaders and pastors. (School B, head of section, personal discussion, May 2017)

This was reflected in the open-ended questions when students were asked about their spirituality and in most of the schools that have Christian Education programs, students reflected that it affected their spirituality. Yet, this was also not reflected as main factor for spirituality (see Table 16).

Some programs are found. Most interviewees reflected having some activities planned like environmental awareness and social events. School A head of section of the middle school expressed:

We are planning and inserting many programs for our students' activities where students can prove more social and leadership skills, yet no specific spiritual skills is developed other than what Christian education and social work are presenting. (School A, head of section, personal discussion, March 2017)

Finally, interviews associated with the findings of both the quantitative data and the two open ended questions with the importance of school climate and its role in the students' life and their spirituality. Students in most Evangelical schools felt loved and accepted and their interactions with their peers and teachers were main factor for enhancing positively their lives in schools. Leaders and teachers, who are in charge of programing and facilitating students' life in schools, found that their students needed to feel spiritual, yet no specific program had been introduced so far.

Discussion

What is the school climate of Evangelical schools like in Lebanon? What are the students' perceptions of their school climate? What is the students' perception of the spirituality in their own schools? Students perceived their school climate as middle-high with mean ranges between 2 and 3. Students in all schools with various

locations and programs, with different demographics and backgrounds described their school climate as being middle-high.

Students generally felt satisfied at their schools. Students of Evangelical schools also described the interaction between peers in their school as moderately positive. Severe violence was not witnessed, and most of the students could express their rights, however with little action taken. Students perceived that their schools' discipline environment was such that for most situations they have a policy, yet they admitted that they were not consistently followed. Schools were mostly clear in their behavioral expectations and most of the teachers used positive discipline, yet they admitted that there was some punishment and shaming, which some students considered necessary. Interactions with teachers were judged as generally fair, with teachers taking the dominant role. Students perceived that the discipline policies aimed to apply rules and order more than improving students' personalities.

Moreover about school climate, students perceived that learning and assessments at their schools were fair. Classes were places for serious academic work. Grades were mostly used to compare students' work to each other. Discussions in classes were initiated by teachers and guided by them. Students perceived that their school's culture and attitudes functioned as part of their society, and some students sought their teachers' advice on topics outside of school subjects. Students mostly perceived that schools were maintaining traditions, however, they sometimes felt that this was irrelevant to their real-life experience.

Multivariate comparisons (ANOVA) data showed that School A students perceived their school climate significantly more positively than schools B and D (Table D2, Appendix D). Relating this to the description of schools presented in chapter 3, differences in factors like physical appearance, size between schools A, B,

and D are found. One also can notice differences in the demographics of the schools, especially those related to socioeconomic and religious ones. Another important difference between the schools is related to the extra programs School A is presenting to students, like sports, character and leadership forming, and social awareness. This difference can also be linked to the study of the role of context and culture in forming students' perceptions about their schools and life as presented by Fowler (1981), Rogers (1951), and Fan, Williams and Corkin (2011). Yet, this difference was not reflected as significant by school C. This might be because the socioeconomic and geographic location of the school and how schools are addressing their students' needs and how students are perceiving them.

Students in Grade 7 in all schools had a lower feeling of spirituality than students of Grades 10, 11, 12 (see Tables D1 and D3, Appendix D). Linking this to the faith development research by Griffith (2001), one can see possible reasons for this variation. Griffith's (2001) presented stages of faith in adolescents searching for identity. One can find that students pass through age stages where they grow in their faith and identity formation and expression. This means that faith and searching for meanings in life is constructive and does not grow over one stage or age in life. Students of Grade 7 had different ways of expressing their faith and spirituality and searching for meaning in their lives than students of grades 10-12. Young teens (12-13 years old) did have different perceptions in life than older teens. This age is obsessed with their peers and they mirror their identity and their life through their peers. Grade 7 or ages 11-12 years old is an age of struggling to form their own identity. They form their identity here based on what they feel and experience and not on what they are told. A study by Vygotsky and Wretsch (1995) and Fowler and Dell (2005) present the factor of age and identity formation.

The students from School A perceived significantly higher levels of spirituality at their school compared to the students in school C. (see Table D3, Appendix D). School A and C mainly differ in the presence of Christian education program in school A and its absence in school C. Besides, school A and C differ in their students' religious demographics. This corresponds to the research presented by both Wright (2016) and Riggers-Piehl and Lehman (2016) concerning the role of religious education in raising spiritual feeling, and spiritual life and orientation of students at schools and universities. Wright (2016) presented the importance of offering Christian religious education and how this can empower many other skills in the life of the students. So, this difference might be related to the presence of a Christian education program in school A. Yet, this cannot prove that with the absence of overt Christian education, students' perceptions of their schools' campuses as spiritual will be minimal or eliminated. Students at both schools, A and C expressed that they do feel moderately spiritual at their schools (See Table 10).

Most of the students in Evangelical schools were positive about their schools' community relations. Of all the school climate subtitles, the school community relations were reflected more positively by students than others. Students perceived their schools as somehow welcoming to their parents and community guests. Their schools have good input to their community in many ways, including providing events like sports and art (see Tables, 5, 6, 7, 9 and 12). In total, students in Evangelical schools perceived their schools as positively acceptable places and centers for learning, interaction, and communications with school peers, teachers, staff, and with community. Students described the climate in Evangelical schools in a moderately positive way. These positive perceptions lead to positive outcomes in the students' academic work, their mental, emotional, and health outcome as presented in

the work of many researchers. However, this was not confirmed only in Evangelical schools, researchers proved that a positive climate leads to positive outcomes in schools of all levels (Cohen, Pickeral & McCloskey, 2009; Durham, Bettencourt & Connolly, 2014; Donovan & Gunnell, 2012; Hanson, 2004; Kidger, Fan, Corkin & Williams, 2011; Marshall, 2004). Positive perceptions of school climates explain the good and broad reputation of the Evangelical schools in Lebanon as institutions with successful academics and positive school culture across varied student demographics (Costa, 2007). This description of positive school climate in Evangelical schools supports the work of other researchers when they suggest that graduates of Protestant schools exemplify higher morale and positive values placed on the individual and the community (Pennings, 2011; Wright, 2016).

The second question is about spirituality. How is spirituality perceived by the students at Evangelical schools? Students in all schools perceive their spiritual health at school as moderate in its two dimensions of God and nature, and slightly higher in what they feel about their spiritual health with others and themselves. What is noticeable is that the students had higher ideals of spirituality than the spirituality they felt at school (see Tables 6, 8, and 10). In effect, the students were saying that what they experienced in spirituality overall at school was lower than what they looked for as ideal. They had higher ideals in worshiping and relating to God than what they experience of Him at their schools. Moreover, student responses showed that what they experienced of spiritual health in schools with others is lower than their ideals or what they looked for. They had higher ideals for kindness, trust, and respect of what they experienced at schools. They had higher ideals for sense of identity, self-awareness, and joy in life, inner peace, and meaning in life than what they experienced in schools. Every person is spiritual and has a need to be. Spirituality is

not an event, it is a trip of searching for meaning in all life, and therefore, ideals for spirituality will always be higher than what people feel of it. This was clear in the studies of Komonchak, Collins, & Lane (1987) and Fisher (1998).

Having higher ideals of spirituality in relation to God does not come from vagueness. Rogers (1951) argues that the context and the backgrounds influence defining perceptions and ideals of God. Sabra (2005) also argues that the Lebanese society is an ideal religious society, meanwhile universities are tending to secularize or neutralize it. Fisher (1998) has highlighted the need of the students to relate to God in their spiritual growth. If we add these concepts together, it means that students of Lebanese Evangelical schools have high ideals for spirituality in relation to God and this is related to their religious context and needs of every person to be spiritual.

Awkwardly, some Evangelical schools tend to secularize or abandon this talk (need to be spiritual or even religious) for many reasons. Kuusisto, Poulter, and Kallioniemi (2016) presented that although every individual holds his or her unique worldview which is not "neutral" but is always value-laden, some try to hide their religiosity and privatize it for the fear of being categorized as religious. In other words, being religious is conceived as being less valuable or weaker.

Schools A and B reflected higher ideals of spiritual health with God than schools, C and D. This may be because Schools A and B have much more extensive Christian education and Bible study programs for their students in comparison to schools, C and D. Schools C and D also have mixed demographics in relation to religion, whereas in Schools A and B most of the students are Christian (see Table 10). Christian contexts support higher ideals related to God where students of mixed contexts can perceive and reflect ideals of God differently (Aldridge & Ala'i, 2013).

Although Schools A and B have programs for Christian Education and Bible teaching, students in Schools C and D also perceived their experience of God at school as moderate, which was the same as in Schools A and B. Ingersol (1994) argues that perceptions of God are different and may relate to many factors other than direct teaching of Him. Community, context, culture, interactions, and many other factors may influence what people experience and perceive of God, as well. Tillich (1967) suggests that all of culture, morality, and religion can constitute the unity of the spirit. Therefore, Christian Education programs can raise higher ideals of spiritual health with God, but cannot necessarily raise higher experiences of Him in Evangelical schools in Lebanon singlehandedly.

The third question this study addresses is about the possible correlation between students' perceptions of school climate and spirituality at Evangelical schools. The results showed a positive moderate correlation between students' perceptions of school climate and spiritual health at schools (see Tables 11, 12 and 13). This result is in line with the studies of Aldridge and Ala'i (2013), Fraser (2014). They all affirmed the relationship between the environment the students live in and the emotional and behavioral products of the students. Assuring a supportive climate and environment will lead to positive emotional and behavioral conduct. The school climate correlates with all its subscales with students' spirituality. This links to the study of Fowler (1981) who emphasized the role of the environment, the physical and emotional, in nurturing adolescence identity, spirituality, and faith. A positive environment with effective discipline and positive interactions between teachers and students, and effective spiritual and religious teachers will help affirm students' feelings of belonging and acceptance, and spiritual health (Fisher, 1998; Rissanen, Kuusisto, & Kuusisto, 2016).

The positive correlation between the culture of Evangelical schools and students' spirituality at schools follow Riggers-Piehl and Lehman's (2016) findings about the positive campus environment in supporting spirituality. The strong positive correlation between school community relations and the spirituality of students at Evangelical schools affirms what Loder (1998), Fowler (1981) and Sheldrake (n.d.) have argued about the role of environment and community as a source of conformity. The community is the source to transform the human spirit, or to suppress it (see Table 12).

The Evangelical school climate in this study positively correlated with their students' spirituality. Evangelical schools can raise their students' spiritual health and nurture them positively while they focus on improving their school's physical appearance, student interactions, attitudes and culture, learning and assessment, a positive discipline environment, and active community relations, since spirituality was found to be correlated with each of these aspects of school climate. By improving and enhancing the school climate at all Evangelical schools, the spirituality of students will be enforced and nurtured (see Tables 11, 12, and 13 and Figure 1). This means that any indicated improvement in school climate can lead to a positive improvement of 25% in the spiritual life of their students. Evangelical schools do achieve moderate spiritual life for their students, yet more positive results in the area of spirituality could result if a positive school climate were more intentionally cultivated.

CHAPTER 5

CONCLUSION

Historically, Evangelical schools were renowned for leading the hearts and the minds of males and females from all religions and sects in Lebanon. The main question of this study on school climate and the spiritual life of the students yielded moderately positive results with positive correlations. The schools' physical and emotional environment were perceived by students as moderately positive. Student-student and teacher-student interactions were also found to be highly important and moderately positive. Academics and assessments, and the learning and teaching environment were also perceived as moderately positive and important. Community relations were perceived as important. Students in all schools in the study perceived their spirituality as moderately important. Whatever students felt, saw, and perceived, and reflected on in these interactions were found to be positively influential. The community, culture and the schools' social environment were perceived by all the schools students as important and as a source of pride and love.

Both school climate and spirituality were considered highly important in previous literature and in findings and studies, as well as for students in Evangelical schools. Spiritual health, was found to be highly noteworthy, and highly necessary. Both school climate and spiritual health can be nurtured when the relational factor is (Young, 1984). One cannot read results of data and their implications without highlighting the main factors which were apparent in all schools. The influential part of both the school climate and spirituality (as presented in both definitions of school climate and spirituality) were highly emphasized in Evangelical schools in Lebanon.

Relationships in Schools Influence Spirituality

In conclusion, results of both quantitative and qualitative data highlighted the following: first, school climate and spirituality are influential in all schools, and correlated with each other. Students in all schools perceived their school climate and spirituality as important.

Second, the intersection of the three types of data, the quantitative (the two surveys), the open-ended questions, and the interviews, concerning students' perceptions of school climate and spirituality highlighted these areas as significant: the interactions and relations of students with their peers, teachers, the community, and the school learning environment. Most of the students felt moderately spiritual in their schools with this feeling directly coming first from positive interactions with peers then teachers, and secondly from Christian programs and Bible lessons, in cases where these existed. The role of community relations is obviously highlighted in both the quantitative and qualitative data. Students highlighted needed activities they love to share with the community (trips, outings, programs, and activities).

A positive association was found to exist between school climate and students' spiritual health in the quantitative data, and in the qualitative data while highly considering the interaction factor and the school community relations too.

Therefore, schools cannot be sure that by presenting good academic programs, combined with any other religious or character building programs, that they can influence the students' spiritual health significantly and provide a positive school climate without achieving positive interactions between students, teachers, and the community. Spiritual health cannot be limited to religious factors only, or to understanding the word of God and the work of the Holy Spirit without the integration of a holistic approach in the students' lives. This is highlighted in the work of Fisher

(1998) in defining spiritual health as relational, including four dimensions: God or the Divine, others, nature, and oneself. Spiritual health in this way is more of an experiential factor. Students in schools need to experience meaning in their lives in relation to God, others, nature, and themselves.

Implications and Practical Applications

Evangelical schools in Lebanon were and still are pioneers in delivering excellent education. The school climate and the students' spiritual health are found by the students to be significantly correlated. Reflecting on the results of this study, I can suggest practical recommendations for the leaders of Evangelical schools.

1. **Positive interactions and communications.** All students brought to attention the interactive factor; therefore, schools are recommended to nurture an environment and climate where students and teachers interact and communicate positively, and where students also are encouraged to interact positively with their peers. Schools are encouraged to plan for activities that can enhance these positive interactions even beyond the classroom borders. These kinds of activities can take shape in different forms and places such as in extracurricular programs, trips, retreats, prayer cycles, mentoring sessions, chapel services and meditations, and private tutoring hours, where students are able to relate to teachers without feeling that their grades are at stake.
2. **Spiritual programs for Teachers.** Evangelical schools are recommended to plan and prepare spiritual programs for teachers, where teachers are equipped to developing sensitivity to the students' spiritual health. Research has shown that teachers are good tools in fostering the students' spiritual health. This can call schools to assess their teachers' developmental programs and to seek to include the spiritual side in their training.

3. **Programs for Christian Educators.** In schools that lead Christian education programs, it is recommended to plan programs for preparing Christian educators to be open minded and lead critical and open discussions. This is for two reasons. The first is related to the religious diversity of the students in Evangelical schools. Students (even in non-Christian demographic schools) expressed during interviews that they need creative open discussions about God and their religious life. Second, it is related to the relational factor highlighted by data where interactions with teachers considered very effective in both school climate and student spirituality. Fisher (1998) concludes that the nature and the belief of the teacher can enforce, enhance, or even restrict the development of the students' spirituality. The teachers are recommended to have a deep understanding of the spiritual and the modern needs of the local students. It is recommended to prepare teachers who can respond to the critical, modern minds as well as to the religious and secular mentality of all students.
4. **Disciplinary Policies.** To achieve an effective school climate, which in turn will support student spirituality, schools are recommended to draw disciplinary policies that are effective and consistent.
5. **Effective community relations.** Since students found the community relations very effective in elevating their school climate, schools are encouraged maintain and at the same time foster more effective community relations where students are involved in their community life projects, and where community members effectively participate in the educational and school activity. This can be through activating different authentic programs, athletic, environmental, social, scientific, and others.

6. **Effective spiritual activities.** Schools are recommended to develop special effective spiritual activity programs for secondary students (ages 15-18 years old). These ages are sensitive ages in forming an identity and spiritual well-being (Tillich, 1967). Programs like self-expression programs, environmental programs, Christian and life talks, mentoring sessions, life activities, and others can be of high value. Omitting Christian education programs and replacing them with other academic sessions or even other social programs may not be beneficial. Evangelical schools' students reflect higher ideals of spirituality in comparison to what students experience in other schools. Moreover, schools with Christian education programs engendered a higher experience of spiritual health than was the case in other schools. Therefore, schools are encouraged to combine various kinds of programs where students are holistically enriched and developed besides their academic training.
7. **Diversity.** Schools are recommended to preserve the culture of diversity where all students from all religions and background feel and perceive that they are welcomed, loved, accepted, and nurtured in mind, body, and spirit. Students with different religious backgrounds reflected that they felt accepted and welcomed at their Evangelical schools. Keeping this feeling up needs efforts to preserve this culture.
8. **Continuous assessment.** Since the context and the environment have a significant role in improving the students' spiritual health, assessing the environment and sensing the students' needs and desires can be very valuable in all Evangelical schools. True continuous assessment of all the school environmental factors, both external and the internal, can suggest clear practical solutions in the development of the students' spiritual health.

9. **Teaching strategies.** Students stated their need to express themselves. All teachers can plan instruction where students can lead class talks. Students can be inspired by their mates' ideas, and directed by their motivating spirits. Teachers need to encourage students and give them space to express their spiritual needs, especially in Christian education and Bible lessons. Students can express their fears, ambitions, feelings, sorrows, and whatever might help them interact and participate, and consequently elevate their spirituality. Teachers need to adapt effective cooperative and collaborative strategies and instruction to fulfill this aim.

In conclusion, school climate and spirituality are two important factors in every school, including Evangelical schools in Lebanon. "Spirituality is innate," and is a need for all students, teachers, and the whole school community (Fahlberg & Fahlberg, as cited in Fisher, 2009, p. 9). School administrators and spiritual life leaders encouraged to assess and evaluate the effectiveness of their school climate and spirituality for the betterment of their students. Activating positive, effective relations between students and teachers is a milestone in achieving positive results in both the school climate and spirituality. Moreover, activating a school climate that touches the whole life of the students will positively influence their spiritual life and the life of the school community.

As a Christian educator and chaplain, I have experienced a need for spirituality in all my classes and with all my students. There is a need for all students to believe that they are loved, accepted, embraced, able to learn and grow, assessed positively, communicated peacefully, and self-expressed through all schools' activities and instructions. Through this academic year, inspired by the results of my study of school climate and spirituality, I changed most of my class instruction in

teaching Christian education, and I gave the chance to my students to express themselves about what they think of God and their lives. I was surprised by the positive feedback I indirectly received from my students, especially when they expressed that they felt more motivated and relaxed. There is a need for all the students to know themselves, their peers, God, and the nature in a climate where they are encouraged to grow holistically. Evangelical schools are fulfilling most of these needs, as perceived by their students, through activating a positive school climate and spirituality, however, for continuous development and change, more efforts are needed.

Recommendations for Further Research

Although this study covered several Evangelical schools and students, there is a need to add more schools. The Lebanese society is rich in all matters, especially the social and the religious. Since the environment and context play a key role in shaping the students' way of thinking and addressing spiritual concerns, adding more schools with various backgrounds and contexts can add clearer, comprehensive results.

This study did not present a comprehensive picture of different school contexts and characteristics, and did not take into consideration how different contexts reflect on spirituality and spiritual experiences. Muslim students come from a context that might understand and define spirituality differently than that of secular or Christian students. So, a comprehensive analysis of the context may help in drawing more effective conclusions.

Also, a comprehensive statistical multivariate analysis (MANOVA) would lead this study to the different interactions between more than two variables together. This will lead the study to find if school climate and spirituality as felt in schools are influenced by these variables (Ages, Grades, Schools) interacting together.

It is important to consider teachers, staff members, and parents also when we think of perceptions of school climate and spirituality. This would lead to a more effective understanding of both the school climate and student spirituality. It is also worth studying spirituality in relation to gender, and the implications for future work in schools.

Furthermore, for more effective educational results of the school climate of the whole Lebanese society, a comprehensive study of the school climate of other Evangelical (Arab and Armenian schools), other Christian (Catholic and Orthodox), and Muslim schools is worth taking into consideration. Moreover, a comparison between these schools on areas such as climate and spiritual programs is worth studying, as well.

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APPENDIX A
INSTRUMENTS

**Examining Students' Perceptions of
School Climate and Spirituality-
Surveys**

The surveys are for a study on Evangelical schools' secondary students perceptions of school climate and spirituality, conducted by Hala Bitar.

Please, answer as honestly as you can the following questions in the open-ended questions and the two surveys about how you perceive the climate and your spirituality at your school. Neither you nor your school will be identified by any way, and the data will be reported in aggregate. Thank you in advance for your cooperation.

Gender: male female

Grade: G7 G8 G9 G10 G11 G12

Age: 11 12 13 14 15 16 17 18

1. Open-ended Questions:

(1) What affects you the most at school?

(2) What influences your spirituality the most at school?

5. Discipline Environment				
Level – 3 (high)		Level – 2 (middle)		Level – 1 (low)
High	high-middle	middle	middle-low	low
5.a	My impression is that the school has a consistent discipline policy		It seems like the school has a discipline policy, but it is not consistent	I see no evidence that the school has a discipline policy
5.b	In my classes the behavioral expectations are clear		In some of my classes the behavioral expectations are clear	I have a difficult time understanding what the teacher expects in my
5.c	Most teachers use effective discipline strategies that are defined by logical consequences and refrain from punishments or shaming		Most teachers use some form of positive or assertive discipline but accept the notion that punishment and shaming are necessary with some students	Most teachers accept the notion that the only thing the students in the school understand is punishment and/or personal challenges
5.d	Classrooms are positive places, and teachers maintain a positive attitude, and follow-through with consequences in a calm and non-personal manner		Most teachers maintain a positive climate, but some days they just feel the need to complain about the class and/or get fed up with the “bad kids.”	Classrooms are places where teachers get easily angered by students and there is a sense of antagonism between the class and the teacher
5.e	I have had some say in making the rules in my class		The teachers make the rules, but consider our feelings	The teachers resent it when we question why a rule exists
5.f	I feel my basic need for power belonging, freedom and fun are mostly met		I can tell the teachers care about my needs, but they are seldom met	Student needs for power, freedom fun and belonging are not respected or considered
5.g	Teacher-student interactions could be typically described as supportive and respectful		Teacher-student interactions could be typically described as fair but teacher dominated	Teacher-student interactions are mostly teacher-dominated and reactive
5.h	When disciplining students, teachers typically focus on the problematic behavior, not the student as a person		When disciplining students, teachers are typically assertive yet often reactive, and give an overall inconsistent message	When disciplining students, teachers are typically personal and often antagonistic
5.i	I feel like I am given a greater degree of self-direction and responsibility. I feel like I am growing as a person		I do not think that the discipline at the school does much to improve us as people, it is just about getting order	It seems like the discipline at the school just tends to make us all mostly hostile over time
5.j	In most of my classes, I feel a sense of belonging and community		I feel that in most of my classes things run smoothly	In most of my classes there are perpetual student behavioral problems

6. Learning/Assessment				
Level – 3 (high)		Level – 2 (middle)		Level – 1 (low)
High	high-middle	middle	middle-low	low
<p>6.a-----○-----○-----○-----○-----○-----</p> <p>I know what it takes to get a good grade in my classes</p> <p>I feel like the grading is fair in the school, but the goals are not always clear</p> <p>It seems like sometimes grades are given for random and personal reasons.</p>				
<p>6.b-----○-----○-----○-----○-----○-----</p> <p>I feel motivated and in control of my learning</p> <p>I feel like I am learning valuable content but I often feel passive and unmotivated</p> <p>I feel like what I am learning is not very valuable, and I am not learning what I do think is valuable</p>				
<p>6.c-----○-----○-----○-----○-----○-----</p> <p>The grading in my classes focuses on both the end result and the process</p> <p>Focusing on the process is encouraged but what is graded is mostly the end result of the work</p> <p>Teachers only seem to care about and grade the final products</p>				
<p>6.d-----○-----○-----○-----○-----○-----</p> <p>In most of my classes my teacher knows my learning style</p> <p>In my classes we do a variety of different kinds of learning tasks, but few or none of my teachers have formally determined my learning style</p> <p>Most of the learning tasks are similar at the school, and there is little or no mention of learning styles</p>				
<p>6.e-----○-----○-----○-----○-----○-----</p> <p>Instruction in my classes is dynamic involving, learner-centered, and challenging</p> <p>Instruction in my classes is mostly based on relevant ideas but often seems to be busy-work</p> <p>Instruction in my classes is mostly based on lectures and tests</p>				
<p>6.f-----○-----○-----○-----○-----○-----</p> <p>In most every class, students learn to work cooperatively and as members of teams</p> <p>In some of my classes the teachers buy into the idea of cooperative learning</p> <p>In most of the classes cooperative learning is seen as leading to chaos and cheating so is rare or non-</p>				
<p>6.g-----○-----○-----○-----○-----○-----</p> <p>In my classes we are encouraged to reflect on the quality of our work and the process aspects of the task</p> <p>Most of the time students tend to focus on what is next and occasionally on the process of the learning</p> <p>Most of the focus is on the product and there are few opportunities to formally reflect</p>				
<p>6.h-----○-----○-----○-----○-----○-----</p> <p>Students are seen as the primary users of assessment information, and assessment is used for the purpose of informing the learning process and is never used to punish or shame</p> <p>Assessment is seen as something that occurs at the end of assignments. Grades are used primarily for student-to-student comparison</p> <p>Assessment is used to compare students to one another and/or to send a message to lazy students.</p>				
<p>6.i-----○-----○-----○-----○-----○-----</p> <p>The discussions in class encourage us to think critically and process concepts</p> <p>The discussions in class are helpful, but mostly related to the facts and the practical aspects of the assignment</p> <p>I feel like there are few class discussions, and those that do take place are mostly teachers dominated</p>				
<p>6.j-----○-----○-----○-----○-----○-----</p> <p>I feel like I learn the subject matter in my classes in-depth</p> <p>I feel like I learn the most essential content in my classes, but not always in depth.</p> <p>I feel like the subject matter I learn in my classes is not very meaningful.</p>				

6 k-----o----- o -----o-----o-----o-----o-----				
Teachers promote the view that intelligence and ability are a function of each students' effort and application, and are not fixed The major emphasis is placed on the process over the product		Teachers promote the view that effort has a lot to do with how much students are able to accomplish. The major emphasis is placed on working to produce good products		Teachers promote the view that intelligence and ability are fixed/innate traits and not all students have what it takes. The major emphasis is on the comparison of products/grades
7. Attitude and Culture				
Level – 3 (high)		Level – 2 (middle)		Level – 1 (low)
High	high-middle	middle	middle-low	low
7.a-----o-----o-----o-----o-----o-----				
At school I feel as though I am part of a community		At school I feel as though I am part of a functional society		At school I feel as though I am an outsider or a visitor
7.b-----o-----o-----o-----o-----o-----				
Students self-correct peers who use destructive and/or abusive language.		Students seek adult assistance to stop blatant verbal abuse		Students accept verbal abuse normal part of their day
7.c-----o-----o-----o-----o-----o-----				
Students feel as though they are working toward collective goals		Students feel as though they are working toward independent goals		Students feel as though they are competing with other students for rare resources
7.d-----o-----o-----o-----o-----o-----				
Students speak about the school in proud, positive terms		Students speak of the school in neutral or mixed terms		Students denigrate the school when they refer to it
7.e-----o-----o-----o-----o-----o-----				
Most students feel listened to represented, and that they have a voice.		Most students see some evidence that some students have a voice		Most students feel they have little voice when at school.
7.f-----o-----o-----o-----o-----o-----				
Most students feel a sense of belonging to something larger		Most students see some evidence that efforts are made to promote school spirit		Most students feel alone alienated and/or part of a hostile environment
7.g-----o-----o-----o-----o-----o-----				
Teachers share commonly high expectations for all students		Most teachers have high expectations for students who show promise		Often teachers openly express doubts about the ability of some students
7.h-----o-----o-----o-----o-----o-----				
Most students feel as though students they owe their school a debt of gratitude upon graduation		Graduates feel that they had an acceptable school experience		A high number of student graduate feeling cheated
7.i-----o-----o-----o-----o-----o-----				
Students feel welcome and comfortable in talking to adults and/or designated peer counselors		Some students have a few staff that they target for advice		Students assume adults do have any interest in their problems
7.j-----o-----o-----o-----o-----o-----				
School maintains traditions that promote school pride and sense of historical continuity		School maintains traditions that some students are aware of but most see as irrelevant to their experience		School has given up on maintaining traditions due the fact that no one cares

8. Community Relations				
Level – 3 (high)		Level – 2 (middle)		Level – 1 (low)
High	high-middle	middle	middle-low	low
8.a -----○-----○-----○-----○-----○-----				
School is perceived as welcoming to all parents		School is perceived as welcoming to certain parents		School is suspicious of why parents would want to visit
8.b -----○-----○-----○-----○-----○-----				
School sends out regular communication to community including invitations to attend key events		School sends out a good amount of basic information to parents		School sends out minimal and basic information to parents
8.c -----○-----○-----○-----○-----○-----				
Community members are regularly invited to speak in classes		Inconvenience leads to few community members speaking in classes		The vast majority of community members have not seen the inside of the school since they went there
8.d -----○-----○-----○-----○-----○-----				
Service learning efforts are regular, promoting student learning and positive community-relations		Service learning is performed but very infrequently due to perceived inconvenience		Service learning is seen as just a glorified field trip and therefore not worth the time or
8.e -----○-----○-----○-----○-----○-----				
Parents and coaches all work for the best interest of student athletes		Parents support the coaches and teams if things are going well		Parents feel free to challenge coaches, coaches mistrust parents
8.f -----○-----○-----○-----○-----○-----				
Volunteer efforts are well coordinated, volunteers are plentiful, and conspicuously appreciated		Volunteers are willing, but are often unaware of the events and/or feel a lack of guidance		Volunteers are hard to find or unreliable
8.g -----○-----○-----○-----○-----○-----				
Athletic events and Fine Arts performances are well attended due to deliberate efforts toward promotion and crowd appreciation		Athletic events and Arts performances are attended by a die-hard following and/or only when things are going well		Athletic events and Fine Arts performances are poorly attended and as a result progressively less effort is made by participants.

ASSC SCAI-S-S Instrument v. 2016 7.4.0 ©Alliance for the Study of School Climate (used with permission)

Spirituality Survey

Spiritual Health And Life-Orientation Measure (SHALOM)©

Directions: Please **give two responses** to each of the following items, by **circling the numbers in each of the two columns**, to show:

- how important you think each area is for your **ideal** state of **spiritual health**, **AND**
- **how you feel** each item reflects your personal experience most of the time.

Each response is graded:

5 = very low **4** = low **3** = moderate **2** = high **1** = very high.

Do not spend too much time on any one item. It is best to **record your first thoughts**.

	Developing		A. Ideal State of Spiritual Health	B. How you feel
1	a love of other people		1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5
2	personal relationship with the Divine/God		1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5
3	forgiveness toward others		1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5
4	connection with nature		1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5
5	a sense of identity		1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5
6	worship of the Creator		1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5
7	awe at a breathtaking view		1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5
8	trust between individuals		1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5
9	self-awareness		1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5
10	oneness with nature		1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5
11	oneness with God		1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5
12	harmony with the environment		1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5
13	peace with God		1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5
14	joy in life		1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5
15	prayer life		1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5
16	inner peace		1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5
17	respect for others		1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5
18	meaning in life		1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5
19	kindness towards other people		1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5
20	a sense of 'magic' in the environment		1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5

Fisher, J. (2010). Development and application of a spiritual well-being questionnaire called SHALOM. *Religions*, 1: 105-121. (With permission)

APPENDIX B

INTERVIEW QUESTIONS

(A) Open-ended Interview Questions for Students:

- (1) What is so specific about your school climate?
- (2) Does the school climate have role in your spiritual life, and in what way?
- (3) What motivates your spirituality at school?
- (4) In order to enhance your spirituality at your school, what do you aspire to?
- (5) In your school, what influences your relationship with God?
- (6) In your school, what influences your Christian based relations with your friends?
- (7) In your school, what influences your relationship with God's creation and nature?
- (8) In your school, what influences your feelings of self-accepted, loved, and belonging to the school community?

(B) Open-ended Interview with the person responsible for spiritual life will be:

General questions like:

- (1) What is your main responsibilities in the school?
- (2) Is there a team who is responsible for the students' spirituality? (3) In case of a team, what are the responsibilities of the team?

Interview Questions:

- (1) How do you describe the spiritual life of your students at school?
- (2) As an Evangelical school, are there specific plans to enhance students' spirituality, what are they?

- (3) What are the programs, activities, curricular endeavors the school directs to enhance students' spirituality?
- (4) At your school, and among all programs and activities, what is the most influencing to your students' spirituality?
- (5) What is the role of teachers in enhancing students' spirituality?
- (6) What is the role of school rules and disciplinary processes in enhancing students' spirituality?
- (7) What is the role of your school specific culture in enhancing students' spirituality?
- (8) Does the school physical appearance target the spiritual life of the students, in what manner?
- (9) Do school learning instructions and assessments support students' spirituality, in what manner?
- (10) Are students encouraged to practice Christian and religious value in their interactions with their peers, in what way?

APPENDIX C

PERMISSIONS

All permissions are taken for the surveys from the authentic resources.

The School Climate Survey Permission

Permission to use the school climate survey from the SSSC was taken on January 2017 from John Schindler the director through proper electronic mailing to: jshindl@exchange.calstatela.edu

Here is the permission mail with proper links.

[Hello Hala,

Sorry for the delay,

Here is the survey link. Do let me know what you would like to change. Also, I will send you a PayPal invoice shortly.

The survey link will not change even if we change the content. So it is set.

Here it is:

<http://www.questionpro.com/t/AEYL5ZYW57>

Also you have a report link that will give you real time results of the survey process. DO NOT give it to anyone. It is for you only.

<http://www.questionpro.com/t/PB43EZYW57>

And consider this email permission to use the survey. Per our agreed conditions and given eventual payment.

John

The Spirituality Survey Permission

Another permission was taken for the spirituality survey from John Fisher through proper electronic mailing to: j.fisher@federation.edu.au

Here is the permission mail:

[A few people have asked for an instrument with less than 20 items. As spiritual well-being is such a complex construct, the 20 items in SHALOM have proved to be a good spiritual thermometer, but attempts to reduce it in size compromise its validity and I seriously doubt any measure that purports to assess spiritual well-being with fewer items. It might take a couple of more minutes to respond to 20 items but the time and effort is more than worth it! Evidence to support this claim and a summary of the development and use of SHALOM is available free on the web as:
Fisher, J. (2016) Selecting the best version of SHALOM to assess spiritual well-being. Religions, 7: 45; doi:10.3390/rel7050045

I look forward to hearing your response as to the suitability of SHALOM for your project, which sounds most interesting.

You might also find the attached QOLIS instrument of help to see how the school compares with home, friends, church and community in providing spiritual nurture.

Best wishes and shalom,

John

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Visiting Professor, Institute of Health, Medical Sciences & Society, University of Glyndŵr, Wales
UK

Hon. Academic Adviser, Centre for Religious & Spirituality Education, Education University of
Hong Kong]

School Permissions

Permission letters were sent through proper electronic mails to all school principals involved in this study and permission was received from all of them. Permission mails will not be posted here due to keeping the school identity and name anonymous in this study.

This is the permission letter:

[Dear Mr.....

I pray you had good day.

I am in the process of writing my Master Degree thesis - MEU. The thesis is covering a research about "Student Perceptions of School Climate and Spirituality in Evangelical Schools in Beirut." >>>>school is one of the great schools in heritage and reputation concerning growing special leaders, academically and spiritually.

The survey needs **25 minutes** with **one section/ group** of students in **grades 7 to 12**. (I am ready to administer all these surveys on acceptable agreed times.)

Short interviews will be done with 2-3 students of each grades between grade 7 to grade 12, and with the head of spiritual life in the school. Interviews aim to support data found in survey and to assure spirituality perceptions relatedness to school climate. In my case at our school, I need to interview you if you accept. The interview with students can be done during recess and upon their own approval, in groups of separately.

The aim of the research is for academic study only. All data of this research will not be used in any way beyond academic field. The individuals and groups' interviews will be respected and students' information will be used here only in a way that do not harass or hurt the school or the individual.

Personal views will not be shared in public, and anonymity of interviewee will be highly considered and respected. The name of the schools will be not titled in all processes since it is not part of the aim of the research and neither the specific demography or religious background of the students. Even if complete anonymity might be impossible for the researcher, confidentiality will be ensured. Data collection will not target participants' personal life issues and experiences. Participants will be asked to answer questionnaires according to their will and voluntary role after or before getting involved in. Individual answers will not be highlighted or used. The reporting of the data will be only in aggregate as group answers.

Comparison between schools will not be done in ways that harass schools' identities or efforts. Comparisons will only be done in recognized positive correlation possibilities between schools' climates and spirituality and their sub-scales.

Attached is the survey, used with permission.

Thank you for all the support and help.

Regards

Hala Bitar [School A, B, C, D, permission letter, February 2017.]

APPENDIX D

ADDITIONAL TABLES

Table D1

Tests Between-Subjects Effects

Source	Dependent Variable	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Model	school climate	3339.211 ^a	46	72.592	206.442	.000
	Ideal state of SH	2336.784 ^b	46	50.800	123.892	.000
	State of feeling of SH	3665.249 ^c	46	79.679	203.830	.000
	Total- spirituality	2948.839 ^d	46	64.105	232.810	.000
school	school climate	2.804	3	.935	2.659	.048
	Ideal state of SH	1.539	3	.513	1.251	.290
	State of feeling of SH	4.700	3	1.567	4.008	.008
	Total- spirituality	.785	3	.262	.950	.416
gender	school climate	.611	1	.611	1.736	.188
	Ideal state of SH	2.167	1	2.167	5.284	.022
	State of feeling of SH	.008	1	.008	.021	.885
	Total- spirituality	.477	1	.477	1.733	.189
grade	school climate	3.824	5	.765	2.175	.056
	Ideal state of SH	2.874	5	.575	1.402	.222
	State of feeling of SH	14.857	5	2.971	7.601	.000
	Total- spirituality	6.406	5	1.281	4.653	.000
Error	school climate	177.222	504	.352		
	Ideal state of SH	206.656	504	.410		
	State of feeling of SH	197.019	504	.391		
	Total- spirituality	138.778	504	.275		
Total	school climate	3516.433	550			
	spirituality ideal	2543.440	550			
	State of feeling of SH	3862.268	550			
	Total- spirituality	3087.617	550			

Sig = or <.05

Table D2

Multiple Comparisons by Schools

Dependent Variable	(I) school of participant	(J) school of participant	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
School climate	school A	school B	.25*	.075	.005	.0590	.4483
		school C	.124	.066	.244	-.0473	.2954
		school D	.22*	.073	.015	.0312	.4120
	school B	school A	-.25*	.075	.005	-.4483	-.0590
		school C	-.12	.071	.273	-.3149	.0557
		school D	-.03	.078	.977	-.2351	.1710
	school C	school A	-.12	.066	.244	-.2954	.0473
		school B	.12	.071	.273	-.0557	.3149
		school D	.09	.070	.506	-.0833	.2784
	school D	school A	-.22*	.073	.015	-.4120	-.0312
		school B	.03	.078	.977	-.1710	.2351
		school C	-.09	.070	.506	-.2784	.0833
Spiritual Health	school A	school B	.07	.066	.662	-.0958	.2487
		school C	-.06	.058	.651	-.2200	.0833
		school D	-.06	.065	.737	-.2352	.1018
	school B	school A	-.07	.066	.662	-.2487	.0958
		school C	-.14	.063	.105	-.3088	.0192
		school D	-.14	.069	.170	-.3229	.0365
	school C	school A	.06	.058	.651	-.0833	.2200
		school B	.14	.063	.105	-.0192	.3088
		school D	.00	.062	1.000	-.1584	.1616
school D	school A	.06	.065	.737	-.1018	.2352	
	school B	.14	.069	.170	-.0365	.3229	

Table D3

Multiple Comparisons by Grades

Dependent Variable	(I) grade of participant	(J) grade of participant	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
School climate	grade 7	grade 8	-.2451*	.07721	.020	-.4660	-.0242
		grade 9	-.0748	.07905	.934	-.3009	.1513
		grade 10	-.1240	.07721	.595	-.3449	.0969
		grade 11	-.1948	.08470	.196	-.4371	.0476
		grade 12	-.1384	.11223	.820	-.4595	.1826
	grade 8	grade 7	.2451*	.07721	.020	.0242	.4660
		grade 9	.1703	.08435	.333	-.0710	.4116
		grade 10	.1211	.08263	.687	-.1153	.3575
		grade 11	.0503	.08967	.993	-.2062	.3069
		grade 12	.1067	.11602	.941	-.2252	.4386
	grade 9	grade 7	.0748	.07905	.934	-.1513	.3009
		grade 8	-.1703	.08435	.333	-.4116	.0710
		grade 10	-.0492	.08435	.992	-.2905	.1921
		grade 11	-.1200	.09126	.777	-.3810	.1411
		grade 12	-.0636	.11725	.994	-.3990	.2718
	grade 10	grade 7	.1240	.07721	.595	-.0969	.3449
		grade 8	-.1211	.08263	.687	-.3575	.1153
		grade 9	.0492	.08435	.992	-.1921	.2905
		grade 11	-.0707	.08967	.969	-.3272	.1858
		grade 12	-.0144	.11602	1.000	-.3463	.3175
	grade 11	grade 7	.1948	.08470	.196	-.0476	.4371
		grade 8	-.0503	.08967	.993	-.3069	.2062
		grade 9	.1200	.09126	.777	-.1411	.3810
		grade 10	.0707	.08967	.969	-.1858	.3272
grade 12		.0564	.12113	.997	-.2902	.4029	
grade 12	grade 7	.1384	.11223	.820	-.1826	.4595	
	grade 8	-.1067	.11602	.941	-.4386	.2252	
	grade 9	.0636	.11725	.994	-.2718	.3990	
	grade 10	.0144	.11602	1.000	-.3175	.3463	
	grade 11	-.0564	.12113	.997	-.4029	.2902	

(Table continues . . .)

Table D 3 (continued)

Multiple Comparisons by Grades

Dependent Variable	(I) grade of participant	(J) grade of participant	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval
Feeling of SH	grade 7	grade 8	-.1209	.08141	.674	-.3538 .1120
		grade 9	-.1984	.08335	.165	-.4369 .0400
		grade 10	-.3571*	.08141	.000	-.5900 -.1242
		grade 11	-.4471*	.08931	.000	-.7026 -.1916
		grade 12	-.5454*	.11833	.000	-.8839 -.2069
	grade 8	grade 7	.1209	.08141	.674	-.1120 .3538
		grade 9	-.0776	.08894	.953	-.3320 .1769
		grade 10	-.2362	.08712	.075	-.4854 .0130
		grade 11	-.3263*	.09455	.008	-.5967 -.0558
		grade 12	-.4245*	.12233	.007	-.7745 -.0746
	grade 9	grade 7	.1984	.08335	.165	-.0400 .4369
		grade 8	.0776	.08894	.953	-.1769 .3320
		grade 10	-.1587	.08894	.477	-.4131 .0958
		grade 11	-.2487	.09622	.103	-.5240 .0266
		grade 12	-.3470	.12363	.058	-.7006 .0067
	grade 10	grade 7	.3571*	.08141	.000	.1242 .5900
		grade 8	.2362	.08712	.075	-.0130 .4854
		grade 9	.1587	.08894	.477	-.0958 .4131
		grade 11	-.0900	.09455	.932	-.3605 .1804
		grade 12	-.1883	.12233	.639	-.5382 .1616
	grade 11	grade 7	.4471*	.08931	.000	.1916 .7026
		grade 8	.3263*	.09455	.008	.0558 .5967
		grade 9	.2487	.09622	.103	-.0266 .5240
		grade 10	.0900	.09455	.932	-.1804 .3605
grade 12		-.0983	.12772	.973	-.4636 .2671	
grade 12	grade 7	.5454*	.11833	.000	.2069 .8839	
	grade 8	.4245*	.12233	.007	.0746 .7745	
	grade 9	.3470	.12363	.058	-.0067 .7006	
	grade 10	.1883	.12233	.639	-.1616 .5382	
	grade 11	.0983	.12772	.973	-.2671 .4636	

SH = Spiritual health

Table D4

Summary of Regression between School Climate and State of Feeling of Spirituality

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.506 ^a	.256	.255	.59129	.256	193.449	1	561	.000

Table D5

School Climate and Spirituality (ANOVA)

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	67.634	1	67.634	193.449	.000 ^b
	Residual	196.138	561	.350		
	Total	263.772	562			

Table D6

Coefficient

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.255	.098		12.854	.000
	school climate	.535	.038	.506	13.909	.000

Figure D1. Scatter plot graph of data distribution of school climate and spirituality.

Figure D2. Normal p – p plot of data distribution, school climate and spirituality.